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Spatial analysis in a giant pockmark field, SE Brazilian slope

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We present the first evidence for a widespread seabed pockmark field across the continental slope of Santos basin offshore Brazil (Figures 1a and b). A recent high-resolution multibeam bathymetric survey revealed over 970 pockmarks across a smooth seabed in water depths between 440 and 700 m. Four patterns of pockmark arrays appear in the data - linear, network, concentric and radial.

Two different approaches were used to analyze the spatial distribution of the pockmarks. In both cases we have used the software PAST, Version 3.04. The first approach was to determine whether the distribution was random or clustered. In this case, we have used the Nearest Neighbour Analysis with Donnelly's edge correction (Davis, 1986). The results indicate a mean distance between pockmarks of 823.15 meters, for an expected distance of 950.02 meters. The R value of 0.86646 indicate a significant clustered distribution of the pockmarks ($p_{\text{random}} < 0.05$).

The clustered pattern is easily seen through the Kernel Distribution using a Gaussian function, for a Radius value of 8230 meters, equivalent to 10 times the mean distance among the pockmarks, with scales giving an estimate of the number of points per area (area per m^2).

The second approach aimed to detect the occurrence of linear alignments which could be associated with the main structures of the continental margin and adjacent continent. For that, we used the continuous sector method, also using a radius value of 8230 meters. The results led to the identification of 251 lineaments, especially in the shallowest areas.

The directional analysis of these alignments, led to the recognition of a significant ($p < 0.05$) preferred direction, aligned according 49.8° (95% of confidence between 42.3° and 57.3°). This value is consistent with the general alignments of the coastline and isobaths of the continental margin, confirming the structural control of the pockmarks distribution.

Figure 1a (left), location of the pockmark field and 1b (right), detail of the pockmark field

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HETEROGENEITY OF REEF HABITATS IN EASTERN BRAZIL

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Brazilian coral reefs have been recognized as an important example of reef growth under marginal environmental conditions. A low diversity coral fauna with high degree of endemism coexists in a transition from a highly siliciclastic muddy environment where shallow banks and fringing reefs are common, to offshore reefs located in a carbonate dominated setting. Along the eastern coast of Brazil, the various aspects that influence the Quaternary evolution of the reefs, created a very diverse suite of reef habitats from the coastal system, of a very shallow continental shelf, to deeper waters of broader banks. This region presents environments that evolved during the Quaternary period in response to climate and sea level changes. These evolutionary changes were controlled by variations in the sediment supply and a geological heritage dating back to the Gondwana break up in South America and Africa during the Mesozoic period. During the Quaternary period, changes in the relative sea level and climate added younger morphological elements such as tidal flats, wetlands, coastal dune fields and coral reefs to the coastal zone. The continental shelf has a relatively low relief and is very narrow (average width from 15 to 50 km), extending up to 200 km at its southern portion forming the Royal Charlotte and the Abrolhos banks where reef habitats abound. The shelf break occurs between depths of 60 to 80 m. The reefs are characterized by their unusual growth forms, which have mushroom-shaped pinnacles that can fuse together on their tops, forming larger reefs structures that include: a) shallow isolated reefs adjacent to the shoreline; b) small bank reefs off the coast with variable sizes (<10 to >20 km) and shapes; c) shallow fringing reefs bordering the coasts of islands; d) open sea coral pinnacles, named “chapeirões”, in depths greater than 20 m; and e) drowned reef ecosystems at the middle and outer continental shelves. The major reef builders are relic forms, remnant of an ancient coral fauna dating back to the Tertiary, and lack completely branching growth forms. Brazilian reefs initiated growth after 8 ka BP, a notable period of coral expansion in the tropical world, but an incipient forced regression related to a sea level decrease of approximately 2-5 m during the last 6.0-5.0 ka, had a significant influence on the evolution of the reef structures, causing a marked heterogeneity seen in the modern reefs. The communities dwelling on the shallow habitats of the nearshore reefs are exposed to strong solar radiation, increasing runoff from nearby continental areas and untreated sewage discharges from expanding urban centers. The bottom sediment surrounding these reefs can reach up to 70% of siliciclastic constituents and rates of sediment accumulation higher than 10 mg.cm⁻².day⁻¹ seem to have been negatively influencing the reef biotic parameters. Adding to this situation it is evidenced, in the last decades, an increase of about 8% in the accumulation rate of this terrigenous mud in the reefs vicinity. These environmental stresses (high input of sediment and nutrient) may have been promoting, in shallow fringing reefs, a macroalgae abundance exceeding 70% of reef coverage (Loiola et al. 2014), and in small bank reefs inside Todos os Santos Bay, it is occurring a phase shift from reefs with satisfactory coral cover to reefs dominated by fast growing zoanthids, which has been negatively affecting the diversity of the reefs fish fauna (Cruz et al. 2015). In the offshore giant chapeirões, from the Abrolhos Bank, which are established in a dominant carbonate province, occur the highest coral coverage and biodiversity of Brazilian reefs, with dominance of endemic species. *Mussismilia braziliensis*, which is the coral with the highest confinement among the Brazilian coral species, dominates in these reefs, with an average cover over 60%, in the last ten years, contrasting with less than 30% observed in nearshore reefs. Drowned reefs with 2-3 m high and low coral cover occur at the border of the continental shelf in depths over 50 m. On the Abrolhos Bank, deep pinnacles and coalescent reefs were recently described and classified as mesophotic reefs (Moura et al., 2013), occurring together with sinkhole-like depressions known as “buracas” (Bastos et al., 2013).

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The distribution of coral habitats in the Bay of Biscay (NE Atlantic): What can geomorphology predict and explain?

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Cold-water corals (CWC) are known to exist in the deep-sea since the 20th century and receive more and more attention. It is suggested that cold-water coral habitats, especially *Lophelia pertusa*/*Madrepora oculata* reefs, are important as feeding-, spawning- and nursery grounds and provide shelter for many other species, including commercially important fish and crustaceans. CWC are however also threatened by human activities, which calls for a better spatial management of those vulnerable habitats.

To this end, habitat mapping is an important tool used in marine spatial planning. Mapping CWC however requires extensive imagery surveys of the seafloor, which footprint is necessarily limited. In order to get regional-scale distribution maps, species distribution modelling (SDM) is thus increasingly used. SDM heavily relies on bathymetry and its derivatives as CWC seem to be dependent on topography and its co-variables such as substrate type, as well as erosion/sedimentation and hydrological processes. In this study, as a step behind SDM, we aim at deciphering the predictive power of geomorphological attributes to predict the distribution of CWC in the Bay of Biscay.

The continental slope of the Bay of Biscay, North-East Atlantic, is incised with more than a 100 submarine canyons. The existence of *L. pertusa* and *M. oculata* has been reported in the beginning of the 20th century by Joubin (1922) and Le Danois (1948). Since then several studies have shown the occurrence of these two and other cold-water coral species and the habitats they build, e.g. reefs.

Ten cruises were performed between 2008 and 2012 to investigate the submarine canyons of the Bay of Biscay. Coral habitats have been established on photos and videos taken by a towed camera or a Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) on 57 dives during these cruises. The habitats are based on the dominant coral group and substrate type. Except *M. oculata*/*L. pertusa* reef, other coral habitats were encountered as well, such as coral rubble, antipatharians and/or gorgonians on hard substrate and sea pen communities on soft substrate. A total of 11 coral habitats were defined according to a typology defined in the framework of E.U. project CoralFish. In parallel, this project also fostered a geomorphological classification of the submarine canyons, using the bathymetry and its derivatives (de Chambure et al., 2013). The classification includes a maximum of 21 detailed classes that are allocated to either a 'canyon' or an 'interfluve' category (Bourillet et al., 2012). The classification has been created at 2 different resolutions and scales: a 100m resolution for the whole Bay of Biscay and a 15m resolution for 4 areas of ca. 25000 km² in total within the Bay of Biscay.

Here we present whether a link can be found between the distribution of coral habitats and the geomorphological classes. We will discuss as well if the geomorphological classification can be used to predict the distribution of habitats at both resolutions (15m and 100m).

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Mesophotic coral ecosystems beyond the southernmost coral reef, South Pacific Ocean

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Extensive submerged fossil reef systems and abundant modern coral communities have been discovered around Balls Pyramid, 23 km south of the known limit of reef formation at Lord Howe Island, southwest Pacific Ocean. Balls Pyramid is a volcanic pinnacle positioned as the southernmost island in an island-reef chain along the Lord Howe Rise, previously considered to be outside reef-forming seas. Detailed morphological investigations of the broad platform surrounding Balls Pyramid have revealed a large fossil reef dominating the mid shelf in 20 – 60 m depth. Basin and channel features occur on the mid and outer shelves, surrounded by platform, reef and terrace features on the outer shelf with a shelf break at 90 – 120 m into abyssal depths > 3000 m. Towed underwater still imagery of the seafloor features have revealed diverse and abundant coral communities colonising the fossil reef structures. Scleractinian corals were found to penetrate to 87 m depth, reaching maximal cover of 84% at 30 m depth on the upper mid shelf reef. Scleractinian corals characterised the upper mesophotic zone (30 – 60 m depth) while black and octocorals characterised the lower mesophotic zone (60 – 115 m). SIMPER analysis identified calcareous sands and encrusting scleractinian corals as the dominant groups contributing to variation of benthic composition across depth classes and seafloor features. The evidence of prevalent scleractinian corals colonising the submerged reef around Balls Pyramid, and the mesophotic depths of coral penetration, demonstrates the importance of the shelf in supporting modern coral growth. The southerly extension of coral communities, beyond the previously known latitudinal limit of coral reef formation, suggests the shelf substrates may hold potential for coral refuge or expansion into the future.

Habitat mapping, towed video and benthic invertebrate assemblages within a marine park on Australia's temperate east coast.

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A decade of mapping seabed habitats along the continental shelf of New South Wales (Australia's most populated state) has delivered 1800km² or a total coverage of 15% of the Marine Estate. In this paper we investigate the relationship between seabed spatial variables, oceanography and patterns of benthic invertebrates based on 2012 surveys at a marine reserve on the temperate east coast. We used towed video, a swath acoustic system and on-board CTD, ADCP and flow-thru systems for surveys across 3 sites and in several depth ranges. Towed video was used to ground-truth acoustics and characterise the habitat forming functional groups across sites. Oceanographic data were examined relative to longer term data and broad-scale climatology. We show that rugosity and aspect were important spatially-derived variables across some depths and sites. While the relative mix of reef, boulder, cobble, pebble and sand explained sponge diversity, depth was important to distribution of sea whips and gorgonians. Over broader scales, deep and discontinuous (>65m) low profile reefs (i.e. Seal Rocks) exposed to strong intermittent and seasonal effects of the western boundary East Australian Current supported dense sponge and sea whip assemblages. Rugose, shallow cobble-boulder inshore reefs adjacent to islands were affected by more localised circulation patterns and supported a mosaic of macro-algae, sponges, ascidians, and urchin barrens at depths <20m. These datasets provide improved understanding of the variability and distribution of non-kelp dominated benthic assemblages and the significance of non-kelp habitat on temperate reefs.

Seabed geology and coastal hypoxia - the Gulf of Finland case

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Coastal hypoxia has increased globally over past decades. Expanded seafloor hypoxia has been linked to increased anthropogenic input of nutrients and enhanced eutrophication of coastal and marine areas (together with global warming). This environmental deterioration is also apparent in the Baltic Sea, a European inland sea and one of the world's largest brackish water areas.

Hypoxia/anoxia could affect marine ecosystem e.g. by reducing biodiversity as well as fish catch. It also affects the ecosystem by facilitating internal loading. Extended and prolonged seafloor anoxia can enhance the environmental problems by releasing toxic heavy metals and nutrients, like phosphorus, from the seafloor sediments, and thus amplify the effects of eutrophication. These adverse effects are problematic especially in the coastal areas, where human pressures are high, and sustainable use of marine resources and health of the seas should be ensured.

In the present work we have used marine geological (seabed sediment and seabed structure/geomorphology) data and other environmental parameters, in order to study the recent environmental history, trends and possible causes of hypoxia/anoxia in the northern Gulf of Finland, the Baltic Sea. A total of 175 sites, from water depths between 5 – 70 m, were studied (2011-2014) using acoustic-seismic surveys (e.g. MBE), surface sediment sampling and video.

Sediment studies (e.g. the lamina/varve counts) and datings (the ¹³⁷Cs determinations) were used to estimate the onset of the hypoxia/anoxia and accumulation of the (latest) laminated sediment unit in the northern Gulf of Finland. Results suggest that in the early 1950's laminated sediments were formed (and preserved) only in the deepest basins of the inner archipelago. Towards the present, laminated sediments were developed also in the shallower basins, thus indicating an overall expanding and shallowing of the hypoxia/anoxia in the area since 1950's. These results support earlier observations from the region. In the northern coast bedrock consists mainly of Precambrian rocks. There the topographical variability leads to patchy and fragmented seafloor. High sedimentation rates (up to 2 cm/yr) and accumulation of organic material in sheltered basins favor oxygen depletion at seafloor, enhancing hypoxia/anoxia development.

These fragmented, heterogenic coastal areas and archipelagoes, and their habitats, are very sensitive to environmental changes. This is a major concern as modeling and sediment proxy results suggest that under the IPCC scenario of a global warming, there is likely no improvement of bottom water conditions in the future in the Baltic Sea. Therefore, our findings should be considered in Marine Spatial Planning, implementation of policy strategies in the environmental issues, and adaptation to future climate change.

This study was made within GTK funded RAUSKU (2011-2014) project and ENPI CBC funded Finnish-Russian co-operation project, the TOPCONS (2012-2014).

Habitat mapping in the Adriatic (Mediterranean Sea) from coastal areas to deep sea: approaches and methodologies for assessing seafloor habitat for sustainable and integrated sea management strategy

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The Adriatic Sea is a narrow epicontinental basin (ca. 200×800 km) in the Mediterranean Sea, divided into three sub basins: the northern Adriatic, a broad shelf with depths shallower than 100 m connected to the biggest lagoon in the Mediterranean sea (the lagoon of Venice), the middle Adriatic shelf basin, (270 m depth) and the Southern Adriatic basin, with a depression of about 1200 m. The primary fluvial dispersal system entering the Adriatic Sea is the Po river, with additional contributions from many smaller Alpine in the north, and Apennine rivers to the south. It is also one of the major sites of dense water formation in the Mediterranean Sea. The physiographically complex Adriatic Sea is home to a variety of benthic habitats, including the shallow oyster reefs and sponge communities in the Venice lagoon, coralligenous formations on the shelf, up to white coral and sponge communities at bathyal depths in the south.

The Adriatic sea is under siege by various impacting factors, such as high demographic pressure on its coastal areas, pollution, marine littering and dumping, fishing practices, ship traffic, harbour activity, and industrial operations which include gas production and offshore sand extraction. In this framework, the habitat mapping is a fundamental pre-requisite for an adequate representation of all physical and biological typologies aiming at a sustainable use and management of the seafloor.

High resolution bathymetry and backscatter data have been acquired systematically in the Adriatic basin over recent years together with a huge number of seafloor samples and images.

We present here the approaches and methodologies developed to map benthic habitat for different case studies, from shallow water to deep sea applied to different scales:

1. The channel of the lagoon of Venice extensively used for navigation purposes;
2. The mid Adriatic shelf for marine sand extraction;
3. The south Adriatic shelf, slope and basin, for establishing representative, comprehensive and efficiently managed MPA networks useful for a sensitive governance of key habitats.

The Adriatic Sea reveal to be an ideal laboratory where to apply integrated habitat mapping procedures working at different scales and in different seafloor settings. In this framework we need to adapt the exiting working methods and to redraw new solutions to obtain results consistent with the knowledge of both biological and sedimentological processes.

Marine Habitats on the margin off Iceland, NE Atlantic as indicated by living Ostracoda (Crustacea)

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North Atlantic can be considered the best studied oceanic region on this planet, but the seas off Iceland are among the least known in this region. The IceAGE (Icelandic Marine Animals: Genetics and Ecology) project aims to investigate benthic habitats of the seas off Iceland, by combining classic taxonomy and modern aspects of biodiversity research, like phylogeography and ecological modelling (Brix et al., 2014). The several collaborators involved in the IceAGE project aim to investigate a wide range of organisms (i.e. meiofauna, macrofauna and megafauna). Consequently, the samples were collected with diverse gear: a multicorer, a boxcorer, two types of grabs, three types of epibenthic sledges, three types of trawls, and one video camera (Brix et al., 2014).

In the present study, we investigate shallow and deep ecosystems, and the relationships of its biotic and abiotic components. We focus on both benthic and benthopelagic realms and use living ostracod crustaceans as a model. Firstly, we perform macroecological analyses on the fauna collected from the shelf to the adjacent ocean basins off Iceland, including the North Atlantic and the Arctic oceans. We characterize the fauna and compare different regions, geomorphological features and three depth zones. We also investigate which of the environmental variables (i.e. temperature, salinity, O₂, sediment thickness, particulate organic carbon flux to the sea floor, seasonal variation of net primary production, latitude, longitude and depth) better correlate with the biological patterns observed. Finally, aiming to contribute to future paleontological studies in the subpolar North Atlantic, we provide several ecological data for the ostracod taxa found in our samples.

In total, 6380 live ostracods and +350 empty valves were studied and identified. These were included in 28 Myodocopa species and 49 Podocopa species in 15 families. Surprisingly, no simple relationship is observed between depth and abundance of the fauna studied, which was collected by RP epibenthic sledges from the margin off Iceland. Usually, fauna abundances diminish with increasing depth. The fauna assemblages living in regions shallower than 1000m differ significantly from both deeper depth zones, i.e. 1000 to 1999m; and 2000 to 2999m, but the latter two deep-sea assemblages do not differ from each other. Concerning the geographical regions, the faunal constituents living off southwestern Iceland do differ from the one living in the northeastern part, probably due to distinct water masses present in the regions. Concerning the relationship among environmental variables (see above) and the fauna, the combination of clay, water depth, and salinity was highly significant (BEST-BIOENV test, Rho=0.68; p=1%). Additionally, the water masses (i.e., Modified North Atlantic Water MNAW 7–8 1C, salinity 35.1–35.3; and Norwegian Sea Deep Water, NSDW <-0.5 1C, salinity 34.91) was another important factor determining the structure of the benthos (ANOSIM, R global= 0,756, p=0,008).

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Assessment of habitat development in the "white coastal band" of the southern and western Baltic Sea based on hydroacoustic surveys

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Till deposits in coastal areas are widespread in the northern hemisphere where Pleistocene glaciations left their remnants. They are building up the southern and western part of the Baltic Sea. Implications of large scale processes like crustal rebound as response of the last glaciation and modern sea level rise can be best observed at coastlines and in shallow coastal areas. As these processes are ongoing, shallow water environments are highly dynamic. The Baltic Sea is an enclosed basin with limited tidal influence, but with a stratified water-body and waves as the main hydrodynamic driving force shaping the seafloor. As the coast is generally retreating, large abrasion platforms have developed in front of active cliffs and on shoals offshore resulting in export of fine fractions towards offshore and the formation of lag deposits ranging from gravel to boulders in shallow water environments. As for marine life areas of a boulders are a different environment compared to the rest of the shore, these parts are forming important living resources for macro-phytobenthos and macro-zoobenthos. Looking more into details, boulder habitats in shallow water environments are exposed to different ranges of wave energy depending on exposition and water depth. Communities on top and sides of boulders are similar but the spaces on the lower edges and beneath boulders provide higher spatial complexity. In exposed areas of the southwestern Baltic Sea boulders are detectable down to 20 m water depth.

From mid of the 19th century until 1974 boulders from shallow submarine coastal areas were commercially extracted from territorial waters of the state Schleswig-Holstein, with 95 % of extracted boulders ranging from 60 to 150 cm in diameter. This resulted in a loss of approximately 3.5×10^6 tons of stones until 1974, corresponding to a total number of exploited boulders of about 2.5×10^6 , equivalent to a loss of 5.6 km² of hard-bottom substrate. For the entire western and southern Baltic Sea a loss of even 100×10^6 tons of stones and boulders was estimated, which equals about 100 km² of hard-bottom substrate. These "stone fishing" activities have changed the sedimentological structures and ecological conditions of the seafloor fundamentally (Schwarzer et al. 2014).

Side-scan sonar surveys carried out since the early 1970s and multibeam echo sounder records carried out since 2006 in coastal waters of the Baltic Sea allow to study temporal variations of seafloor conditions for a period of more than 40 years and the recovery of the seafloor after the human impact. However, these surveys were limited to areas deeper than 6 - 8 m below the water level. For comparison of old analog data and modern side-scan sonar records with different recording techniques and acquisition of navigation, the method developed by Kubicki and Diesing (2006) was applied. Due to coastal retreat and simultaneously lowering of the seafloor measured by scuba divers in a monitoring program newly exposed boulders could be observed with an increase in the number of boulders up to 125 %.

It is well known that the shallow areas between the coastline and approximately 10 m water-depth belong to the so-called "**white coastal band**", an environment, where geodiversity and variability increases, resulting in small scale spatial sediment distribution and habitat patterns. Unfortunately, most habitat mappings do not extended to the coastline and only limited observations and measurements exist from these shallow areas, especially from wave dominated environments due to rough physical conditions. Investigations in shallow water environments require special logistics and flexibility as there is no access with research vessels having a lot of surveying techniques hull mounted. The program (GeoHab-BALDESH - *Habitats and boulder-fields along the coast of Schleswig-Holstein - their dynamics and functioning*) which started in 2014, covers the spatial gap by filling up the lack of information to link these ecologically very important and highly variable areas to the already mapped regions. Instruments for high resolution seafloor mapping (Side-scan sonar, subbottom profiler, multibeam echosounder and sediment classification system) will be towed to a specially

designed catamaran behind small boats. Results, focusing on the detection and functioning of boulders will be presented.

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Biodiversity and Geodiversity in the Continental Shelf of NE Brasil:

the Macroinfauna off the Açu River, Rio Grande do Norte state

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The continental shelf of the State of Rio Grande do Norte (RN) comprises different relief structures, such as submerged dunes, reef banks, valleys, which is inhabited by a rich community of benthic invertebrates. The present study is part of the INCT AmbTropic, a consortium of Brazilian research groups which activities focus on diverse aspects of the marine environments off Northern and Northeastern Brazil. Herein, we aim to characterize and evaluate the benthic macroinfauna from features with distinct sedimentological characteristics off the Açu River, RN. Three areas were studied, each one with a different types of substrate. Area 1 is located West to the Açu River Valley and is characterized by bioclastic sands (carbonate content > 70%). Area 2, on the valley, shows terrigenous (carbonate < 30%) to bioclastic (carbonates > 70%) mud. Area 3, on the East of the valley, shows silici-bioclastic (30-50% carbonates) to bio-siliciclastic (50 to 70% carbonates) sands. Ten sediment samples were collected in each of the areas with a VanVeen grab (0,01m²) in May 2014 (rainy season). The collected material was fixed in 70% ethanol and sieved through 500µm mesh, all animals in these sieved samples were picked and identified.

The significance of differences in density of individuals, the Shannon diversity and Pielou evenness was tested with ANOVA 1-way and Fisher's Least Significant Difference a posteriori. The abundance data was fourth root transformed and the Bray-Curtis similarity was calculated among samples. The structure of the data was visualized in a non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) and tested using the ANalysis of SIMilarities (ANOSIM). The SIMPER analysis showed which taxa contributed most to groups of samples according to the three environments. A total of 1009 individuals from 36 taxonomic categories were identified. Polychaetes were the most abundant (49% of subjects), followed by bivalves (14%), amphipods and oligochaetes (both 9%). The average density of organisms varied significantly from Area 1 ($70 \pm 37 / 0,01m^2$) > area 3 ($35 \pm 18 / 0,01m^2$) > Area2 ($8 \pm 6 / 0,01m^2$) (FAreas [2.27]: 15.8 p > 0.05). The highest Shannon diversities occurred in bioclastic and siliciobioclastic sandy bottoms (both 1,7nats / ind) (areas 1 and 3), follow terrigenous mud (area 2) ($1 \pm 0,3nats / ind$) (FAreas [2.25]: 8.2 p > 0.05). However, the equitability showed no significant difference among sedimentary features (FAreas [2.25]: 1.9 p < 0.05). The nMDS indicates that the assemblages inhabiting the distinct environments are significantly distinct (Figure 1C, RGlobal = 0.54; p < 0.05). The SIMPER analysis shows that despite the polychaetes dominate the three areas studied, amphipods were highlights in terrigenous mud area; bivalves, the Tellinidae family, were the highlights in siliciobioclastic sand; oligochaetes and stood out in bioclastic sand (Figure 1C). These results indicate that the grain size may determe the structure and composition of benthic macroinfauna in the continental shelf of RN, where the terrigenous mud, with finer particles, show a less diverse and dense macrofauna assemblage. In this area, amphipods are dominant possibly because they find ideal conditions foraging. Environments with sandy bottoms (Areas 1 and 3, respectively west and east of the valley) tend to harbour denser and more diverse faunas, possibly because of greater availability of microhabitats. Thus, the different types of sediment seem to be a good indication of the infaunal communities that inhabit the shelf off Açu River. Knowledge of the geohabitats seem to have

predictive value, particularly if biological indicators such as density, diversity and community structure are monitored over time. Thus, the next step of our study will compare the macrofauna of the continental shelf of the RN state in the two seasons (rainy and dry).

Harnessing Earth Observation for large scale aquatic habitat mapping

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Earth observation has been applied to environmental mapping and monitoring for several decades. However, mapping the seafloor with earth observation still presents considerable challenges. Standard image classification techniques cannot be directly applied to imagery of submerged targets since the overlying water column distorts the spectral information.

The solution to this is a physics-based approach which fully describes the satellite sensor signal in terms of the key parameters of water column depth, water column optical properties, and seafloor reflectance (Figure 1). Such approaches are however quite sophisticated to develop and implement, and typically require significant computational power. Often in the R&D stage, they are applied to relatively small areas (10's to 100's of square kilometres). The alternative, where large regional scale aquatic habitat mapping is done using earth observation, is to conveniently ignore the confounding effects of the water column and apply standard classification techniques to the imagery, resulting in errors.

Our physics-based method, the Modular inversion Program (MIP), solves for the three key parameters, producing high resolution digital maps of satellite-derived bathymetry (SDB) and seafloor reflectance (SFR). Importantly, it has been implemented into an operational and robust processing system, which allows for large areas (1000's of square kilometres) to be efficiently mapped. Here we present a selection of successful, large scale aquatic habitat mapping projects using MIP on high resolution satellite imagery, including (but not limited to): all of the shallow waters of Abu Dhabi (Figure 2), the Mexican section of the Mesoamerican Reef System, all of Ningaloo Reef, and the entire Great Barrier Reef. Summarizing broadly, the bathymetry has an accuracy of within 10-20% of validation data, and the benthic cover maps (~10 to 15 classes) were judged to be correct for ~75% of the classified pixels in the imagery. The methods and results of this work, as well as the implications of this technology will be presented and discussed in more detail.

Figure 1. Seafloor reflectance draped over bathymetry, Mesoamerican Reef System, Mexico.

Figure 2. Satellite-derived habitats displayed via online GIS system of Environmental Agency of Abu Dhabi

Mapping EMUs (Ecological Marine Units)

– the creation of a global GIS of distinct marine environments to support marine spatial planning, management and conservation

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A steering committee formed under the auspices of the intergovernmental Group on Earth Observations (GEO; <http://www.earthobservations.org/geoss.php>) met at the offices of ESRI in Redlands CA on 25-27 February to progress the development of a global map of ecological marine units (EMUs). This work builds upon an earlier terrestrial classification and map (Sayre et al., 2014) of ecological land units (ELUs; http://www.aag.org/cs/global_ecosystems). At this inception meeting our goals were to explore concepts of a coupled pelagic and benthic classification (Costello, 2009) and review existing classification schemes as well as build a unique, 3-dimensional GIS of relevant existing data sets with which to map EMUs.

The committee endorsed an approach that encompasses classifications of the seafloor and water column as separate but interlinked domains at a spatial resolution of 1 km². It was agreed that the classification should be based mainly on physical data. For the seabed, key classifying variables are depth, seabed slope, geomorphology (Harris et al., 2014), bottom water temperature, dissolved oxygen, particulate organic carbon flux, solar irradiance, carbonate chemistry and bottom current regime. The committee adopted 9 horizontal benthic zones: 1. coastal; shelf (2. low, 3. medium and 4. high relief); 5. slope; abyssal (6. plains, 7. hills and 8. mountains); and 9. hadal. For the pelagic zone, key classifying variables from available data sets (Davies and Guinotte, 2011) are depth, temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, primary production, particulate organic carbon flux, carbonate chemistry, solar radiance, water clarity (k490), surface currents, wave regime, tidal range and sea ice cover. The committee adopted 15 water column volumes divided into surface, epipelagic, mesopelagic and deep pelagic where they intersect the 9 benthic horizontal zones. One application of the EMUs is as a standardized partitioning of marine space and abiotic characteristics to understand and predict biotic distributions using species distribution data (for example). Plans are to produce a draft map of EMUs by the end of 2015.

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The role of habitat in MPA assessment

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Protected areas have been increasingly recognised as important tools to meet both conservation and management goals. There is a growing awareness that the effectiveness of marine protected areas (MPAs) needs to be established in order to allow for informed management decisions to be made and to promote their use as a management tool. In this study we investigate the effect of a small marine sanctuary on a localised population of southern rock lobster (*Jasus edwardsii*) (SRL). Previous studies have established that MPAs commonly have a positive effect on SRL populations by increasing biomass and number of individuals but data to determine whether this is a consequence of differences in seafloor characteristics or biological assemblages is often unresolved. This study integrated ultra-high resolution multibeam echo sounder data, videography and commercial fishing data to assess SRL populations within an MPA (Merri Marine Sanctuary) and surrounding waters. Study results indicate that the Merri Marine Sanctuary (MMS) supports a higher abundance of both under-size and legal-size SRL and that these SRL are generally larger in size and biomass. The effect of seafloor characteristics, biological habitat and distance from MPA was tested using GLM models. The results of this study indicate that the MMS has a significant effect on local SRL population size even with variations in depth, slope, rugosity and distance from park taken into consideration. Additionally, more SRL were captured closer to the park suggesting the potential of a spillover of SRL biomass into surrounding waters. The completion of this research has provided valuable information about the effects of protection, seafloor characteristics and biological habitat on a localised SRL population and demonstrates how remotely sensed techniques combined with commercial fishing approaches can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of MPAs. Ranging in size from small targeted coastal zones to vast pelagic areas (>100,000 km²), In addition MPAs pose many challenges when assessing their function in protecting biodiversity. We explore new opportunities for the habitat mapping community such as animal borne remote sensing to better understand the role of MPAs in protecting the breeding and foraging grounds of resident and migratory species and important linkages between existing MPA networks.

Mapping habitat for data-deficient marine species: Atlantic Wolffish in Conception Bay, Newfoundland and Labrador

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Rare marine species are often urgent targets for conservation efforts. However, small populations, inaccessible habitat and limited understanding of their distributions pose significant challenges to conservation managers. This project studies Atlantic Wolffish (*Anarhichas lupus*) habitat in Conception Bay, Newfoundland, Canada, as a case study mapping the habitat of a rare marine fish to support conservation planning. Atlantic Wolffish have been included as a species of Special Concern under Canada's Species At Risk Act since 2003. They were widely distributed throughout the North Atlantic and parts of the Arctic, however this distribution is increasingly fragmented and populations are often too small to accurately calculate population dynamics or project recovery rates. Habitat requirements of the species, fine-scale distribution, and their vulnerability to anthropogenic impacts remain poorly understood.

The study area covers 27km² of coastal waters, ranging from 5–180m in depth, in Conception Bay, Newfoundland. Fisheries and Oceans Canada (DFO) conducted a wolffish telemetry study between June 2011 and August 2012 using 34 Atlantic Wolffish implanted with internal acoustic transmitters and an array of 11 VEMCO hydrophones moored throughout the area. Four wolffish den sites, where the fish feed, spawn and guard developing eggs were also identified in the study area through SCUBA diving.

High-resolution multibeam data were collected using a Kongsberg EM710 by the Canadian Hydrographic Service in July 2013. Ground-truthing for bottom type and benthic species was conducted between July and October, 2014 through SCUBA diving (video and still images), ship-based Deep Blue Pro drop video and Van Veen benthic grab sampling. An approach similar to Brown et al. (2012) benthoscape method was used to create benthic habitat maps. First, the ArcGIS 10.1 ISO algorithm was used to conduct an unsupervised classification of multibeam backscatter, bathymetry, slope, and curvature. This classification identified six substrate classes. Second, biological communities were identified through PRIMER-E MDS, ANOSIM and SIMPER analyses of georeferenced video and grab sample species abundance. The six bottom types were then merged into a habitat map reflecting three distinct biological communities.

Statistically distinct benthic habitats identified in this study are “mud and silt”, “muddy gravel and cobble”, and “mixed bedrock and boulder” habitats. Mud and silt habitats are characterized by deep (>100m), low slope areas dominated by infaunal invertebrates (e.g. *Nephtys cornuta* polychaete worms), *Chionoecetes opilio* snow crab and *Caprella spp* seastars. The muddy gravel and cobble habitat is found throughout mid to deep ranges (50-180m) with a biological community dominated by the brittle star *Ophiopholis aculeata*, anemones (*Urticina* and *Stomphia spp*), and urchins (*Strongylocentrotus spp*). The bedrock and boulder habitat (<60m), is characterized by higher slopes and a mix of cobbles, boulders and bedrock. Coralline algae (*Lithothamnion articus* and *Melobesiodae spp*), and *Agarum cribosum* kelp and *Membranoptera alata* algae are common. The megafaunal community on the bedrock-boulder habitat is dominated by

Stronglyocentrotus droebachiensis urchins, *Asterias vulgaris* seastars, and blue mussels (*Mytilus* spp). The overall accuracy of the resulting habitat map is 93%, calculated using an error matrix (N=30).

Telemetry data indicate that Atlantic Wolffish in Conception Bay have high home range fidelity (<4km range) and most individuals were present throughout the 16 month survey period. Atlantic Wolffish dens were found within the bedrock and boulder habitat, specifically in or immediately adjacent to areas of high slope (30-60°) and high density of prey species (*Stronglyocentrotus* spp. and *Mytilus* spp.). The four observed dens occur between 15-18m water depth, just below the mid-summer thermocline, often near the boundary between exposed bedrock and cobble-boulder talus. All known wolffish dens are all within 50m of each other. Due to the low spatial variability and the small sample size of observed dens, these data cannot generate reliable statistical distribution models for wolffish denning habitat. Potential denning habitat, however, was identified by classifying areas of similar geomorphological profile (backscatter, bathymetry and slope, change in slope) to the known dens. This analysis indicates that 1.6 km² (5.9%) of the study area offers potential denning habitat for Atlantic Wolffish. While this may be an over-prediction, it provides a testable hypothesis for researchers seeking to collect more data on Atlantic Wolffish distribution and life history. This information will also be used to guide further field surveys and has been provided to conservation managers.

High-resolution seafloor mapping in the German Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ): present state, developments and challenges

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In recent years the demand for detailed knowledge on the distribution and the characteristics of sediment types especially in connection with benthic habitats has increased. Following European Union directives, the European coastal states are obliged to identify, assess and monitor marine conservation zones as well as threatened and protected biotopes. These areas and other heterogeneous regions with mixtures of soft and hard bottoms require an extensive basis of precise data. Areas with gradual changes that develop no sharp boundaries are in the particular need of clear demarcation rules in case the results shall serve as the basis for habitat-size information.

To accomplish this task on a modern scientific basis a team of marine geologists headed by the German Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH) developed standardized interpretation and classification strategies for different seafloor types. Therefore, full coverage mapping surveys using sidescan sonar systems were performed and ground truthing was carried out using grab samplers and video devices.

The draft of the standardized, national guideline for seafloor mapping and classification includes specifications about data collection, processing as well as data interpretation and finally seafloor classification and discrimination. This enables the creation of a consistent layer set of defined sediment types. Thereby, much more reliable information on the heterogeneity of the seabed are provided which supports the understanding of benthic diversity and mapping marine benthic biotopes. However, certain aspects are not standardized by now. The most critical point is the detection and delineation of boulder fields. Setup of clear criteria is needed since the localization of boulder fields is a main issue for marine nature conservation as well as environmental impact analysis and locating suitable cable routes

The guideline is presently tailored to support German governmental marine mapping tasks in the EEZ. However, it should be extended for mapping specifications applied in coastal zones where e.g. a smaller mapping scale is needed to reflect the higher dynamics. In a further step it is planned to parallel the guideline with similar efforts of the European partner countries in order to aim at a true European effort in producing standardized maps that can easily be connected across the borders of the European coastal countries.

Ecosystem Services Assessment from the Carmel Mountain to the Sea: A multi-disciplinary method for defining ES indicators in coastal and marine landscape units

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Methodologies for the identification, quantification, and analysis of ecosystem services (ES) are developing rapidly throughout the world. Despite the growing use of ES assessment to value natural landscapes exposed to development pressures, successful practical applications are few. In this pilot project, we assess the benefits of different types of ES along a gradient of land- and seascape units (terrestrial, coastal and marine). The research emphasis is on development of the methodology for practical application suitable for scaling up from the local level to the regional level and including the territorial near shore area of the Mediterranean Sea along the chosen transect that serves as the area of interest. The transect passes from the Carmel mountains to the outer extent of the territorial waters of the country (12 nautical miles from shore). As such, the pilot realizes the ES assessment across distinct landscape units using GIS data and various algorithms for evaluation. Our research goals are threefold: 1) successful evaluation of various mapped ES using categorical indicators based on the literature and on available data; 2) practical scenario development based on planning conventions; and 3) integration of our first two goals for the delivery of a method that can be used on a wide scale across landscape units. Products consist of a compilation of GIS-generated maps of the study area— an approximate 200 square kilometer area transect with about a third of this area being marine. The final products of the research are a series of spider graphs (based on the GIS layers and statutory land use plans and marine plans of varying spatial and temporal scale). These graphs show relative losses and gains in ES services according to areas slated for development in land and sea use plans. The method's products serve as the basis for weighing trade-offs in ES across relevant land- and seascape units in the Mt. Carmel region of Israel. The methodology implemented serves as an example of how ES assessment can be used within the existing planning regulatory framework and institutions and also highlights the challenges of mapping ecosystem service indicators in the marine environment as opposed to the terrestrial environment where both existing condition data and scenarios can be more readily mapped.

Designing Marine Protected Areas Management Plans: Using Spatial Conservation Prioritization Methods

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Spatial conservation prioritization (SCP) is well on its way to becoming an important tool for the planning of protected areas. Using SCP, areas of spatial investment can be indicated in multi-tiered management plans. The spatial analyses conducted as part of SCP methods use traditional types of quantitative data with new types of qualitative information. This research (conducted within the framework of EU-Funded Marie Curie Action: Designation and Management of Marine Reserve Networks; see <http://demarn.net.technion.ac.il/>) explores the use of physical elements of the environment and their spatial character together with innovative qualitative data to inform the design of management plans for marine protected areas. We posit that SCP often neglects human needs and institutional constraints in spatial analyses. Therefore, our goal is to identify institutional and societal constructs frequently left out of marine protected area design when SCP methods are used. Research conclusions are based on comparison of outcomes. As a case study, we use the Rosh HaNikra marine reserve in the north of Israel. This existing small marine protected area is slated for significant expansion. We compare outcomes of a spatial multi-criteria analysis (SMCA) with outcomes arrived at through the use of MARXAN software. We then compare these outcomes to the management plan currently under consideration for statutory approval by the Northern District Planning Committee. Each of the approaches used for developing a management plan emphasizes certain aspects of conservation planning. These are respectively: stakeholder preferences, expert opinion and real-world political and institutional constraints. Through the comparison of spatial outcomes we identify differences related to those aspects of SCP that are missing or neglected by the tools used. Preliminary results suggest that uncertainty of data (especially at relatively great bathymetric depths), contested national boundaries, and distrust of public processes are limiting institutional factors in the design of marine protected areas management using SCP.

MacroBenthic Diversity as Impact Indicator for Managing Changing Systems in Santos Bay

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The Santos Bay is one of the most preeminent region in South America. It can be classified as a typical sub-tropical mangrove system under significant anthropogenic pressure. Santos Region is a densely populated conurbation in Southeast Brazil, with over 1.300.000 inhabitants living on its coastal urban zone. This ecologically significant estuary ecosystem harbors South America's busiest seaport, as well as an important petrochemical complex, a metallurgical complex, and intense tourism and fishing activities. The demand for environmental licenses for new businesses is intense and the current format of evaluation reports is inappropriate. It makes it impossible to aggregate the evaluation of various topics together to produce integrated knowledge on the functioning of the system. To fill this gap we are building a geoportal, called SantosWebAtlas. It developed and standardized methodologies to provide macrobenthic richness and diversity data shown color-coded on maps (Fig. 1). It includes all the available past data in the theme and organizes them in an easy-to-access database. Once put together the geographically referred data is used to generate fresh information. It allows correlation between interdependent themes and evaluates the impacts with an integrated and multidisciplinary approach. This true effective knowledge can lead to better and well-supported decisions.

The result of this work also provides visibility and transparency in the licensing processes. The data available in a simple to visualize and yet comprehensive language can greatly improve the people understanding on the topics.

The main goals of the SantosWebAtlas (<http://santoswebatlas.com.br/>) is integrate information from a variety of sources and thus help the management policy to improve the examination and monitoring of specific areas.

The geoportal has a form (<http://santoswebatlas.com.br/mapas/questionario/questgoogle/>) which users can evaluate the information and thus give us feedback on what we can improve.

Figure 1 – Integration researchs data Tommasi (1979), Heitor (2002) and CODESP - FRF (2008), about macrobenthos diversity. An understanding of cause and effect is made possible by integrated mapping studies. Note: Geoportal allows access in interactive query, improving the observation in time and space.

Juvenile fish habitats: integrating science, GIS, and local knowledge to inform community-based management in Hawaii

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Nearshore fish populations are in decline in the main Hawaiian islands, and in recent years there has been greater emphasis on the value of ecosystem-based local management. This project integrates science, technology, and local knowledge to provide a basis for effective community-based resource management in a rural Hawaiian community. We test the hypothesis that juvenile reef fish are significantly influenced by seascape variables, such as composition of surrounding habitat types. Set in the context of existing local knowledge of near-shore resources, nursery habitats for juvenile reef fishes – areas of particular ecological value for sustaining fisheries resources – are assessed in a quantitative manner, supplementing the information upon which management initiatives were based. To better understand underlying ecological patterns and processes, we conducted fine-scale *in situ* ecological surveys in addition to applying a spatially-explicit approach based on detailed benthic habitat maps produced using GIS and remote sensing methods. Canonical correspondence analyses were used to assess fish-habitat relationships, and habitat metrics were found to be influential on juvenile reef fish abundances. Depth, macroalgal cover, coral cover, and distance to shore emerged as primary influential factors. Furthermore, some fish species were more influenced than others by seascape factors. Habitat associations of two important food resource species in the study area of Hā'ena, Kaua'i, the convict tang (*Acanthurus triostegus*) and the redlip parrotfish (*Scarus rubroviolaceus*), were identified, providing spatial distribution information valuable for resource management planning. This quantitative ecological study played an important role in the successful approval of the Hā'ena fishery management plan by the state governing agency. An ecosystem-based management approach, informed by multiple knowledge sources, will help to ensure the sustainability of fisheries and maintain the societal benefits provided by the ecosystem.

Seascape ecology and conservation: using habitat mapping to improve Marine Protected Area design.

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Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) have been highlighted as an effective conservation strategy against the continued decline in global marine biodiversity. In order to effectively protect biodiversity, the design of MPAs (their location, configuration and size) should be guided by the best available ecological knowledge. Currently in Australia and many other parts of the world, MPAs are designed on CAR principles. The CAR principles ensure MPAs are 1) comprehensive, including all ecosystems across the bioregion, 2) adequate, with the correct level of reservation and 3) representative, areas included reflect the biodiversity of the ecosystem. Due to the significant cost and time involved in sampling marine communities over the spatial scales required for MPAs, mapped habitat classes (e.g. rocky reef, seagrass, mangroves, unconsolidated sediments, etc.) have become increasingly used as surrogates to indirectly determine marine biodiversity and guide MPA boundaries. Often MPAs are established by adequately (>30% of area) representing each habitat class within the bioregion of interest. However, this design criterion has no consideration of the effect of broad-scale seascape patterning of these habitats (shape, size and configuration) on marine biodiversity. Similarly this approach does not consider the importance of fine-scale structural complexity of habitats (rugosity) on marine assemblages. Without adequately representing these scales of spatial heterogeneity, MPAs may not be effectively protecting biodiversity and ecological processes. In this study we sought to test the importance of seascape patterning and habitat structural complexity on the fish assemblage of two MPAs; the Jervis Bay Marine Park and the Lord Howe Island Marine Park, NSW, Australia. We used aerial photography, towed video and high resolution multibeam data to calculate a range of seascape and complexity indices. Baited remote underwater video stations were used to survey the fish assemblage. Preliminary findings indicate that habitat connectivity is an important driver of the fish assemblage within the Jervis Bay Marine Park, with reef fish abundance and diversity being positively correlated to the amount of seagrass in the local seascape. To date, our results suggest that the seascape and structural complexity are important drivers of the spatial patterns in fish assemblages. This indicates the potential of habitat mapping to improve the design of MPAs to reach conservation objectives in a cost-effective and time efficient manner.

Seafloor Backscatter Acquisition and Processing : Best Practice and Recommendations from the Backscatter Working Group

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The Backscatter Working Group (BSWG) was established following the GeoHab 2013 conference's workshop on the use of backscatter data provided by seafloor-mapping sonars. All attendants from a range of scientific domains, including researchers, engineers, sonar manufacturers and software developers supported the launch of the working group. To date, more than 120 people expressed a direct interest in the work undertaken by the BSWG and registered to the group email address. The purpose of the group was to document and synthesize the state-of-the-art in sensors and techniques available today and to propose methods for best practice in the acquisition and processing of multibeam sonar backscatter data.

The BSWG has since worked on preparing guidelines for operators, scientists and end-users as well as recommendations for sonar manufacturers and software developers. Over 20 people actively contributed to the report writing. The resulting document entitled "*Backscatter measurements by seafloor-mapping sonars: Guidelines and Recommendations*" is organized in seven chapters coordinated by a lead-author and written by groups of specialist:

1. an introduction to backscatter measurements by seafloor-mapping sonar;
2. a chapter providing a background on the principles of sonar and physical backscatter, with some fundamental definitions;
3. a discussion on user's needs based on a short survey from a wide spectrum of community end-users;
4. a review on backscatter measurements by actual bathymetric echosounders;
5. an analysis of best practices in backscatter data acquisition ;
6. a thorough review of backscatter processing principles with details on present software implementation;
7. a synthesis and a number of key recommendations.

The release of the BSWG final report at GeoHab 2015 concludes this ambitious two-year project. Designed to reach a wide audience of scientists, engineers, operators and stakeholders using sonar backscatter data for seafloor-mapping applications, the BSWG report includes fundamentals of the topic, a review of state-of-the-art techniques, and a number of recommendations for future systems and processing software.

The paper reviews the BSWG mandate, structure and work program; it details the various chapter contents; and emphasizes the conclusions of the report and in particular its recommendations to end-users, sonar-system manufacturers, and developers of processing software. We will discuss the future of the group and possible new initiatives, in particular the development and implementation of standardized procedures for sonar calibration, and data acquisition, processing, and representation. This is so that the BSWG may expand and evolve for the benefit of all stakeholders.

New algorithm for multibeam imagery processing

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Multibeam backscatter has only recently come to the forefront as a regular product in a variety of industries with access to multibeam survey systems. Whether a backscatter product is the primary survey mission, or simply a by-product to maximize efficiency through shared data gathering, there has been increasing need for a robust post-processing pipeline workflow to generate accurate, normalized imagery products from this collected data.

CARIS HIPS and SIPS 9.0 provided a new, intuitive platform with simplified workflows for processing multiple types of acoustic imagery. The next iteration of this platform will introduce a new processing algorithm to automatically produce fully compensated multibeam backscatter mosaics using industry-standard techniques and corrections tailored to each sensor's characteristics. This algorithm pulls real-time sonar parameters directly from the raw data, minimizing user inputs. The imagery is compensated for Time Varying Gain (TVG), transmit power and receive gain, and normalized through a robust estimation of the area ensonified by each sonar beam. The beam pattern is also computed and applied during mosaic creation, reducing again the intervention needed from the user.

Each compensation step is supported by industry-accepted acoustic notions and is fully documented. Users can therefore be confident that the process will result in the best possible imagery without the need for multiple passes with manual user corrections.

This new algorithm and workflow will be described in this paper and demonstrated through applicable use cases and comparisons.

Reducing track-line artifacts in amplitude mosaics using empirically-derived, whole-survey gain normalization

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Modern swath-mapping sonars with bathymetric capabilities produce sonar image mosaics with high topographic quality. Despite the geometric accuracy, the quality of the imagery is often less than satisfactory because the beam-forming designs tend toward complicated directivity diagrams which are prone to modulate the amplitude data collected and result in striated images at constant angles relative to the ship's track. Calibrated directivity diagrams are available for some instruments and can be used to compensate the sonar imagery for these artifacts, but in general, most advanced processing schemes commercially available today appear to rely on empirically deriving the residual angular compensation values. If the empirical compensation factors are based on stacking only a relatively few pings from each track (either as a fixed or running value), then the resulting sonar imagery may be internally consistent within each track, but will tend to drift between tracks, especially on complex terrain. This drift between lines, if present, can ruin a sonar image mosaic of an extended area.

Considering the speed of modern computers and the wealth of detailed geometric information available about each sample in a bathymetric data set, there is no reason to optimize the estimation of angular compensation residuals to just a few pings in each track. Instead, I propose scanning the entire data set to empirically derive a gain normalization table—in essence, an empirically-derived directivity diagram—that is valid for the entire data set. Calibrated systems will only see modest improvement in the imagery, but uncalibrated or poorly characterized systems can see dramatic improvements in mosaic quality. Even imagery from compromised systems can be improved (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Empirically-Derived Gain Normalization Table. The gain table shows the mean residual (relative) amplitude values as a function of depth and across-track distance from the sonar transducer. The table was derived by stacking all pings from 70 track lines collected from 150 m to 600 m water depth (more than 6.4 million soundings). The port transducer was operating with two transceiver boards with blown fuses, which explains the lower residual amplitudes observed on the port side of the swale. This defect can now be compensated for during post-processing of amplitude data.

Backscatter Patch Test – inter-comparison of systems using shared reference areas for testing, calibration, and quality assessment

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The European Union Marine Strategy Framework Directive (“MSFD” Directive 2008/56/EC, Official Journal of the EU, 25.6.2008) requires member states to monitor and assess the health status of their marine habitats. Due to their ability to provide simultaneous bathymetry and backscatter strength (BS) reflecting the seabed nature, multibeam echosounder systems (MBES) are by now the standard technology for doing this legal obligation. However, while IHO standards provide a clear framework for assessing the quality level of the bathymetry, there is no formal quality level scale for the BS and consequently, no level of reliability of the final decibel values, the unit of BS. As highlighted by the document “Backscatter measurements by seafloor-mapping sonars - Guidelines and Recommendations” from the Backscatter Working Group, evaluating the BS quantitative capabilities to monitor the seabed integrity, measuring the level of quality and defining standards for BS quality are current challenges. To move forward on these topics, five European teams, from Belgium, France and United Kingdom, have started a project on the definition and validation of reference areas in order to perform BS “patch tests” (mean and variance estimation of each MBES); relative (and possibly absolute) calibration of different MBES; inter-comparisons between different acoustic measurement systems; and to record long-term time series of reference data. In addition, repeated surveys combining MBES with an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler are organized. The latter measures currents and backscatter in the water column allowing studying the potential influence of water column conditions on the BS. Vertical profiling of oceanographic parameters is also conducted. Based on this pooling of BS related datasets, BS reliability and stability will be assessed. Key reference areas, proposed by the teams involved in this project, are shown on the map below.

The three shallow-water zones have already been the subject of numerous bathymetric and BS surveys using different acoustic systems with *in situ* control (video and samples) of the seabed nature. The resulting time series already enable a detailed characterization of the bathymetry, morphology and geological characteristics, and are a first step for BS stability assessment. In the framework of GEOHAB 2015, the main purpose of our contribution will be to present a detailed description of the reference areas, illustrated by previous data from sonar surveys (high-frequency MBES) and ground-truthing operations. We will describe the criteria that are ideally needed to establish a reference area for the BS, with focus on this relative calibration approach to characterize in detail the quantitative measurements of BS. The next step of the project is to include a cruise by a single vessel over the three areas, and the building of a shared data library.

Detection Of Stones In Marine Habitats Using Hydroacoustics

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Hard substrates in sublittoral environments are hotspots of marine biodiversity; especially for benthic communities. It is habitat and shelter for flora and fauna, including rare species endangered by threats such as fishing. For fishes, marine mammals and birds hard substrate areas are important breeding and feeding places. In offshore areas those habitats are mainly represented by cobbles and boulders (stones) often located in wide areas of soft sediment. The localization and description of stone occurrences also gains increasing importance for politics. Detailed distribution maps are relevant for resource assessments, coastal management and protection conventions. So far no clear definition and consistent demarcation criterion exists for stony grounds / reefs in the national and international literature. Descriptions like “high concentration of stones” or “reef like structures” are very vague and not sufficient for habitat classification and modelling after e.g. EUNIS or HELCOM HUB standards. Demarcation criterions such as the distance between the objects or a number of objects on a certain area do not exist so far. For both approaches at least the localization of single objects is necessary. Identification of hard grounds through trawling, grab sampling or video inspection is insufficient due to the patchy occurrence of such habitats. Generally, a good method to detect objects at the surface of the seafloor is provided by area-wide sidescan sonar imaging. Elevated objects block the sonar pulse causing high backscatter at the front and an acoustic shadow (no backscatter) behind the object. The shadow length is strongly related to the location of the object relative to the sidescan sonar and the object height. However, objects close to the sonar fish have a shorter shadow compared to objects of the same size located farther away. Hence, objects close to the sonar’s nadir may remain undetected because they produce shadows below the data resolution. Further limitation in the detection of objects is caused by sessile communities living on objects such as stones. The bio-cover absorbs and scatters most of the acoustic signal so that the typical high backscatter at the front of the object is not present. Areas of benthic communities, which are related to hard substrates, can be detected by single beam seafloor classification systems thus supplementing sonar data. Conventional single beam systems have a relative large footprint in deeper waters (e.g. ~4.5 m at 25 m water depth) which limits the precise detection of smaller objects. A smaller foot print is given by parametric sediment echo sounders. The nonlinear acoustic propagation enables high resolution (decimeter) data with small footprints (~1.5 m at ~40 m water depth) at low frequencies (e.g. 8 kHz).

Identifying objects like stones in sidescan sonar data is mostly related to visual-manual, time consuming procedures. To develop an automated identification and demarcation of stone fields, sidescan sonar and parametric echo sound data were recorded within the marine protection area “Outer Reef Sylt” (German Bight, North Sea) in May 2013. The investigated area (~ 3.000 km²) is characterized by heterogeneously distributed moraine and marine deposits. The glacial sediments (here: medium sand to gravel size) are partly covered by Holocene marine sediments (here: fine sand size) that form a patchy and thin drape. Sidescan sonar data reveal stones either in areas of highly heterogeneous substrate (fine sand, coarse sand, gravel) or in wide areas of fine sand. In such places parametric sediment echo sounder data indicate hyperbolas at the sediment surface (fig. 1). Extensive ground truthing data, especially high quality underwater videos, show that these hyperbolas are caused by objects such as stones (mostly densely populated) lying on the sediment surface. The locations of the hyperbolas fit very well with areas of stone deposits observed with sidescan sonar. An automated procedure to identify and export the hyperbola positions makes the demarcation of stony grounds reproducible, faster and less complex in comparison to the visual-manual identification on the basis of sidescan sonar data.

Figure 1: Parametric sediment echo sounder data showing signals (encircled) at the sediment surface caused by stones.

The use of multibeam backscatter as a means of identifying faunal assemblages in a deep-sea cold seep

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In chemosynthesis based deep-sea ecosystems such as hydrothermal vents and hydrocarbon seeps, species distribution is often tightly linked to highly localized environmental conditions. Even a very basic understanding of the functioning of such ecosystems, is, therefore, dependent upon reliable mapping of the fauna and habitats. Imagery is the obvious choice for characterizing these systems and has indeed proven extremely valuable towards furthering our understanding of seeps and vents. However, the acquisition of detailed images with resolution sufficient for species identification is extremely time consuming and labor intensive. It requires precision at a number of levels; speed, maintenance of an appropriate altitude, adequate lighting (which can vary based on species), etc., many of which, such as angles or zoom levels, need to be pre-determined through testing which in itself can be quite laborious. Despite the best laid plans, it is rather common for gaps to occur in imaging transects of mosaics of a study area. In light of the various technicalities associated with the acquisition of appropriate image based datasets, we developed a novel method for mapping cold seep fauna and habitats. Our method uses multibeam echosounder bathymetry and acoustic backscatter data, both segmented and reclassified based on topographical features and then combined to obtain a raster containing unique values incorporating both datasets. This provided a relatively fast and efficient way of characterizing deep-sea cold seep habitats. The method was applied to a cold seep community located in a pockmark in the deep Congo channel and we were able to ground truth the accuracy of our method against images of the area. To our knowledge, this is the first time such a method has been developed for use in deep-sea cold seeps and could potentially lead to mapping of cold seeps on a much larger scale than was earlier possible.

Mapping benthic substrate in Northern British Columbia (B.C.)

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In response to potential growth in the transport of hazardous goods along the coast of Canada, the Canadian government has implemented a multi-agency World Class Tanker Safety System program. As part of this program, the Department of Fisheries and Oceans (DFO) Science division has been tasked with mapping benthic ecosystems in areas of Northern British Columbia (B.C.) that may be affected by tanker traffic. In response, DFO has conducted ROV research surveys in May and October 2014 in Douglas Inlet and will continue in 2015 within the Gwaii Haanas National Marine Conservation Area Reserve and Haida Heritage Site. One objective of these surveys is to ground truth predicted classes of benthic substrate derived from bathymetry and backscatter data (provided by the Canadian Hydrographic Service).

In this study we have explored various classification algorithms for predicting bottom type including those methods employed by the Benthic Terrain Modeller (BTM) tool (Wright et al., 2012). Following this method, we combined multibeam bathymetry and its derivatives (ie. Slope, Bathymetric Position Index) into numerical class codes that represent geological zones such as peaks, depressions, flats and slopes. In addition, we incorporated backscatter mosaic data (acoustic intensity) and its derivative metrics (unsupervised isocluster, Gray-Level Co-Occurrence Matrix GLCM) to further classify the bottom types (bedrock, cobble, gravel, sand and mud). The empirical data (ROV observations and bottom grabs) were used as training classes to revise our classification algorithm.

Improvements to this method would include an evaluation and assessment of the relative importance of the input derivatives that contribute to the final predictions. Recently, there have been developments that help address this need through a standardized approach for classifying data that include machine-learning algorithms. In a paper by Hasen et al. (2014), he described and applied a geostatistical model approach that integrates backscatter angular response, backscatter mosaic and bathymetry using Random Forests (RF) to map benthic habitat. Similarly, we applied RF to a study area in B.C. and preliminary results suggests that further investigation is worthwhile and may potentially lead to a more objective and automated approach for predicting seafloor bottom types.

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Figure 1. Map of study areas for the Tanker Safety System surveys

Classification of tidal channel substrata with high resolution multibeam data, OBIA and ground truth data. Case study from the Venice Lagoon, Italy

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Bathymetry and backscatter data from Multibeam Echo-Sounder (MBES) give a lot information about characteristics of the seafloor. Recent developments of acoustic devices and computing power have substantially improved the resolution of bathymetry and backscatter intensity measurements.

The results of the post-processing of MBES data are raster images based on pixels. Application of Object-Based Image Analysis (OBIA) tries to connect pixel-based analysis and object topology (Lucieer, 2012) in order to perform precise automatic classification of the seafloor and creating benthic habitat maps. OBIA works similarly to the human eye that collects similar pixels in an image into groups, and discern different shapes and spatial relations (Hay and Castilla, 2006; Weise, 2012). Image objects can be created as areas in segmentation process from pixel-based information. After segmentation they could be commonly used for classification. Recent studies have consistently compared supervised classification methods in order to classify backscatter MBES data (Ierodiaconou et al., 2011; Che Hasan et al., 2012; Stephens and Diesing, 2014). Here, we present the results of different classifications methods for an extremely shallow tidal lagoon channel seafloor.

In 2013, a tidal channel of the Venice Lagoon, Italy was surveyed using Kongsberg EM2040-DC MBES with unprecedented detail (up to 5 cm grid resolution). The channels of the lagoon were almost unexplored before. To extract all possible information from these MBES data, a multiresolution segmentation algorithm was applied to the dataset. This segmentation created image objects to be classified (Lucieer et al., 2013; Diesing et al., 2014). Several classifier algorithms were applied to classify the backscatter and bathymetry image in various ways. They are: Classification and Regression Trees (CART), Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Bayes, K Nearest Neighbor (KNN), and Template Matching. Most of them require additional information from ground truth samples to perform semi-automatic classification of the seabed. After the comparison with ground truth data, KNN seems to give the best supervised classification with respect to the others. Moreover, we show that, for specific types of substrates, the application of the Template Matching method improves substantially the classification.

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HABITAT MAPPING THROUGH TEXTURE ANALYSIS ON THE CONTINENTAL SHELF OF THE MALTESE ISLANDS

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Shallow marine areas are the most affected by human activities. Consequently, it is necessary to map marine habitats to better manage resources and ecologically important areas (e.g. MPAs, Natura 2000 sites, etc).

The seafloors around the Maltese archipelago were investigated in the last years (2009-2012) through four multibeam surveys. A large amount of high-resolution multibeam bathymetric and backscatter data were produced and analysed to produce a benthic habitat map of the continental shelf north-east of the archipelago and a portion of the continental shelf off the north-western coast of the Island of Malta.

The seafloor morphology of both the areas (ranging in depth have been from 2 to 402 m on the east and from 2 to 154 m on the west) have been quantitatively analysed through the Benthic Terrain Modeller (BTM) toolbox for ArcGIS. The Zone Classification Builder tool of BTM takes into account the Bathymetric Position Index (BPI) and the slope classifying the seafloor in four classes: crests, depressions, flats and slopes.

The backscatter data have been analysed through TexAn software – implemented by the University of Bath – which analysed the acoustic textures and variations occurring within the backscatter imagery. The product of this analysis is sediment map of the Maltese continental shelves, complemented with grab samples in key areas.

The combination with seafloor morphology and morphometric analyses produces a ground-checked map of potential habitats in these areas.

Imaging fluid seeps using water-column backscatter data in New Zealand sedimentary basins

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Seafloor fluid seeps offer an environment propitious to endemic and chemosynthetic biological communities to develop. They can also be a window into hydrocarbon processes occurring at depth as seafloor and near seafloor features can indicate seepage of fluids enriched with methane and other hydrocarbons. Fluid seeps are often identified from water-column acoustic flares detected as phase differences in multi- or single-beam echosounder data, associated carbonates can be identified as localised patches of high acoustic backscatter on the seabed, and fluid expulsion features or pockmarks on the seafloor can be identified in high resolution bathymetry. Globally, fluid vents are being identified at a rapid rate in many locations across the world's continental margins, aided by multibeam echosounder systems capable of mapping water column scatterers in 3D.

Acoustic imaging of gas seeps exploits mechanical resonance gas bubbles in the seawater and the large acoustic impedance contrast these have with the surrounding seawater. Processing the large volumes of data collected remains challenging and is a new and evolving field. The same approach that is well established to processes seafloor backscatter can be applied to water column data.

Large water-column backscatter data sets have now been collected from New Zealand sedimentary basins, and widespread fluid venting has been identified within some of them in particular along the East Coast of the North Island. A standout of investigations to date is the discovery of over 100 gas flares in a 50 km² area on the outer shelf (100-300 m deep) offshore of Poverty Bay. Sampling of seep fluids offers the opportunity to analyse gas geochemistry and potentially distinguish between biogenic and thermogenic methane sources with implications for the presence of hydrocarbon source rocks. Research is now underway to quantify the methane flux from the Poverty Bay vent field and determine the source mechanism and migration pathways leading to this exceptionally prolific and high density vent field.

Fine-scale benthic habitat mapping in extremely shallow water: comparison between MBES backscatter segmentation methods and ground truth

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Recent technological developments of multibeam echosounder systems (MBES) allow mapping of benthic habitats with unprecedented detail, including in extremely shallow waters, challenging to map with instruments often designed for deeper waters. With very high-resolution (down to 5-cm grid) bathymetry and co-located backscatter data, it is now possible to map the spatial distribution of very fine scale benthic habitats. In fact, the resolution is such that the characteristic signature of a single sponge can be distinguished. In this context, it is necessary to understand which of the commonly used segmentation methods is best suited to account for such detail. At the same time, new sampling protocols for very precisely geo-referenced ground truth data need to be developed to validate the benthic substrate classification. In order to classify the backscatter data, we compare both pixel-based and object-based image segmentation methods, namely Maximum Likelihood Classifier, Jenks Optimization clustering, textural analysis by TexAn, Object Based Image Analysis by eCognition) and the signal Angular Response Analysis of Geocoder in QPS Fledermaus. The methods are applied on a dataset collected in an extremely shallow (< 1 m) tidal channel of the Lagoon of Venice, Italy.

Up to now, the lagoon tidal channels had remained almost unexplored, despite their distinctive geomorphological and ecological features, their importance for water and sediment exchange with the open sea, and their utility for navigation purposes. Through a large number of precisely geo-referenced ground truth data (grab samples, underwater photographs and videos), we were able to identify five different classes of the substrate composition, including sponges, mixed submerged aquatic vegetation, mixed detritic bottom (fine and coarse) and unconsolidated bare sediment. The results of the backscatter classification obtained with the different approaches were validated against the ground truth data. We estimated the degree of agreement between the classes identified with the backscatter segmentation and those defined with the high spatial resolution seafloor samples. As a result, we are able to assess the advantages and limits of each method, and identify which are the most efficient for fine-scale benthic habitat mapping in extremely shallow waters. This assessment opens a totally new perspective in the monitoring of benthic habitats in view of a knowledge-based management of natural resources in coastal areas.

Physical and biotic factors influencing the sessile invertebrate communities on deep-sea dropstones

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Abstract: The deep sea consists largely of homogenous soft-bottom habitats, but this sea of mud is punctuated by islands of hard substratum. Hard-substratum islands come in all sizes – from landscape structures like seamounts, to a sea urchin test that can be held in the human hand. In polar regions, dropstones are released by melting glaciers or icebergs and become important hard-substratum islands on the deep seafloor, inhabited by a variety of sessile and encrusting invertebrates. In order to understand the distribution patterns of dropstone fauna, several classical hypotheses from the terrestrial island literature were tested, in particular the assembly rules of Jared Diamond. The results showed a significant relationship between species richness and the size of a stone. Some species were also found to preferentially settle on larger stones, while others were found on different sizes of stones in proportion to their abundance. Dropstone fauna were found to be non-randomly distributed, with some pairs of species being found together more often than expected by random chance and some species pairs being found together less often than expected by random chance. Dropstones were more densely populated at a station adjacent to a deepwater rocky reef, where many of the same species occurred in great density. The distribution of sessile invertebrate fauna on deep-sea dropstones depends both on physical factors such as geology and stone size, but also on biotic factors such as competition and commensalism.

The development of an Environmental Variability Index (EVI) to scale sampling effort in marine habitat mapping

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The need for a strategy for optimal allocation of sampling effort in marine habitat mapping programmes is becoming more widely recognised as one way to make surveys more cost effective as well as providing more representative information about the seabed. An optimised strategy should allow sampling effort to be scaled based on changes in environmental and spatial variability; increasing sampling effort in heterogeneous areas and decreasing the effort in homogeneous areas. The Norwegian offshore seabed mapping programme MAREANO currently samples 10 stations (video lines at all and physical samples at 2 of these 10 stations) per 1000 km², regardless of the complexity of the environment. As the environmental and spatial variability of the Norwegian seabed has become better known, the need for a more flexible strategy has become increasingly apparent.

In response to this need for flexibility the development of an Environmental Variability Index (EVI) was initiated by MAREANO. The purpose of the EVI is to provide a quantitative standard basis for scaling the national sampling effort to environmental and spatial variability. The EVI can be used to guide sampling effort both for long-term strategic planning on a national scale as well as for detailed cruise planning in more local areas. It is designed to account for the environmental dispersion estimated from the coefficient of variation of the environmental layers (e.g., bathymetry, oceanography).

The EVI appears to pick up important environmental and spatial variability related to the physical environment, however, in practical terms it needs to correlate well with spatial turnover of biological and geological diversity. To test this correlation we applied linear models using either beta diversity (species turnover and nestedness from video line observations) or beta geodiversity (here measured as sediment grain size turnover and nestedness) as response variables and the EVI as the predictor. We found that both were positively correlated with the EVI. These results are promising and highlight the potential of EVI to properly scale sampling effort. Further testing in new areas as well as development of better diversity measures (especially related to beta geodiversity) is needed to prove the general validity of the EVI.

Spatial patterns of biodiversity on Carter Seamount, Eastern Equatorial Atlantic; scales and drivers

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Seamounts are prominent, globally distributed seafloor features, which are often considered as “hotspots” hosting diverse benthic communities and abundant fish stocks. Concerns about the effects of human impacts, such as bottom trawling and potential seabed mining, have necessitated the development of appropriate management scenarios. However, those need to be underpinned by a thorough understanding of biodiversity spatial distribution, and the environmental drivers which shape the structure of seamount communities.

Here, we investigate differences in benthic community assemblages in relation to seamount bathymetry & derived parameters (rugosity, BPI etc.) in conjunction with oceanographic variables at Carter Seamount in the Eastern-Equatorial Atlantic (200 -1900 m water depth). The study is based on a comprehensive nested dataset collected during the ‘TROPICS’ cruise on board the *RRS James Cook*, and is linked to the ERC Starting Grant projects CACH and CODEMAP (grant nos 278705 and 258482). Shipboard multibeam and backscatter data is combined with ROV-video records, high-resolution bathymetry and voucher specimen samples, in addition to extensive water column characterisation by CTD and filtration. Carter Seamount exhibits a rich benthic megafauna with particularly diverse coral gardens between 680-1220 m depth. Preliminary results suggest strong assemblage zonation governed primarily by the dominant substrate type and slope angle. Future analysis will reveal the role of water-masses and derived chemical parameters and temperature in affecting the zonation patterns observed.

Local-Scale Hydrodynamic and Sedimentological Influences on Cold-Water Coral Reef Development

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A positive feedback mechanism resulting in the formation of complex morphological structures on the seabed is developed when cold-water corals (i.e. *Lophelia pertusa* and *Madrepora oculata*) and hydrodynamics interact (Roberts *et al.*, 2009). In recent years, giant cold-water coral carbonate mounds, particularly on the Irish continental margin and north east Atlantic, have been studied in detail. However, in the northeast Atlantic, smaller, isolated and clustered patch-reefs are more frequent i.e. the Moira Mounds and the Darwin mounds. In light of this abundance, the Belgica Mound Province (BMP) has been subdivided into four regions based on the geographical occurrence of 256 patch-reefs referred to as Moira Mounds. It has been hypothesised that these small patch-reefs may represent an early-stage "start-up" phase of the nearby giant coral carbonate mounds.

The morphology and development of cold-water coral (CWC) reefs are primarily controlled by sediment baffling through hydrodynamic-topographic interaction. While previous work has demonstrated this effect on a regional scale or across large coral carbonate mound structures (i.e. Galway mound)), this study examines a localised (<10 km) chain of patch-reefs and their sedimentary environment to better constrain the processes which affect CWC reef development and heterogeneity. Here, ROV-derived video data, surface-sediment samples and oceanographic data are utilised to develop a seabed zonation. 3 distinct zones are defined based on mound health and occurrence, sedimentary environment and hydrodynamics. Based on the results, each zone demonstrates a differing set of hydrodynamic, sedimentological and substrate-related attributes which give rise to various mound sizes, morphologies and vitality. Furthermore, we build on previous work relating to CWC reef sediment-trapping capabilities, in particular, discerning the relative contributions of sediment-trapping and *insitu* biogenic sediment to vertical reef growth across an environmental gradient. This reef chain-scale variability research is part of a Ph.D. project examining CWC reef development on various scales (single reef, local, regional and temporal).

Origin of high densities pockmark fields in a marine reserve and their use in inferring near-seabed current

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Pockmarks have been observed around the world's ocean and lake beds for decades. They indicate shallow and/or deep sub-surface fluid seepage, and may occur in isolation or in groups. Dense fields of pockmarks were identified in three areas (510 km²) mapped using multibeam sonar in the Oceanic Shoals Commonwealth Marine Reserve, located in the tropical Timor Sea on the Australian continental shelf. The pockmarks occur in flat, barren, silty plains (~105 m water depth) which surround extensive carbonate banks and terraces (~40-75 m water depth). The banks hosted rich communities of benthic organisms including sponge gardens and corals. A distinctive feature of many of the pockmarks in this area is a linear scour mark that extends up to 200 m from pockmark depressions. Previous numerical and flume tank simulations have shown that scouring of pockmarks occurs in the direction of the dominant near-seabed flow. These geomorphic features may therefore serve as a proxy for local-scale bottom currents, which may in turn provide information on sediment processes influencing biodiversity patterns in the region.

In this presentation, we: 1) provide information on the methods used to characterise and count the scoured and non-scoured depressions (i.e. an automated method involving ArcGIS spatial analyst tools); 2) draw on other datasets to provide information on why the pockmarks developed (e.g. multibeam backscatter and geochemical variables); and 3) investigate their potential as an environmental proxy (oceanographic) for benthic habitat studies

The analysis of multibeam bathymetry revealed over 200,000 pockmarks, which occurred at densities of up to 2800/km². Such high values were only reported in temperate waters and mainly related to buried glacial sediment. High density occurrences correlated with low backscatter intensities, a distinctive angular response curve (ARC), finer grain-sizes and proximity to banks. Solid-phase TOC concentrations and pore-water total carbon dioxide concentrations (TCO₂) were also elevated in the regions of high pockmark densities. Indeed, porewater TCO₂ concentrations, when normalised to porosity, were about two times higher in these sediments than in other sediments from around Australia. We propose that labile organic matter shed from raised features primes the mineralisation of abundant particle bound TOC, thus enhancing porewater TCO₂ concentrations and causing gaseous efflux from the sediments.

Scour marks related to the pockmarks were analysed and results reveal that they record bi-directionality predominantly trending E-SE to W-NW (~30% each direction). The spatial pattern of scour marks also suggests that currents are redirected by the raised carbonate banks, leading to locally varied flow directions and "shadowing" in the lee of the larger banks. To assist with the understanding of the processes contributing to the formation of the scour marks, a regional oceanographic shelf model incorporating tides was constructed to calculate bed shear stress over a three month period across the mapped areas. Results show that for most of the modelled time, bed shear stress exceeds the minimum value for erosion of consolidated cohesive sediments (0.1 N/m²), thus supporting pockmark scouring. In addition, the results suggest that at a regional scale, seabed currents are dominated by tidal flow and focused in the SE-NW sector (295° as the dominant direction) and that small differences in the predominant modelled directions between each mapped area exist. The latter two findings correlate with the observations. Given the strong agreement between the regional model results and the pockmark observations, the fine-scale variations observed give insight into seabed processes at a scale finer than model resolution, and have the potential to contribute to explaining benthic community distribution.

Figure 1: Backscatter image overlain with hillshaded relief showing pockmarks and scour marks surrounding the foot of a carbonate bank. Blue: Low dB and red: high dB

Figure 1: Benthic communities mapped from the GeoEye-1 image of Lady Musgrave Island. A. Lady Musgrave Island and reef platform (152°24'E; -23°54'S), southern Great Barrier Reef (red box) where fieldwork was undertaken from May 13th – 29th, 2014. B. A Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the Lady Musgrave reef platform, depicting the island, lagoon basin, wide reef flats, elevated algal rim and steep forereef slopes down to the deeper shelf at an approximate depth of 23m (vertical exaggeration factor of 50).

Characterization of the Nesting Beaches of *Olive Ridley* Sea Turtle in Orissa Coast and development of Habitat Suitability Models in the Bay of Bengal

Dr. Neena Priyanka^{1,2}, Dr. Nishant^{1,2} and Dr. P. K. Joshi^{1,2}

The mass nesting of Olive ridley sea turtles in the Orissa coast generally occur during the month of November to March every year. It was expected that perhaps the beach condition of the turtle rookeries such as Gahirmatha, Devi and Rushikulya rivers mouth are more conducive for mass nesting. However, the population size of sea turtles during the mass nesting varies from time to time due to frequent changes in the coastal landscape, geomorphology and adjoining seascape. The present study was carried out for characterisation of the Olive ridley sea turtle nesting beaches from the sea water line in Ganjam (Rushikulya river mouth) and Baleshwar (Gahirmatha) region in Orissa to understand the determining landscape factors of mass nesting. Landsat satellites images of periods 1990, 2000 have been used for this study. Supervised classification had been used for preparation of land use /land cover map using two date data (2000 and 2008). The spatial distribution of major land use /land cover classes which have been identified are settlement with vegetation, plantation, sandy area, dense mangrove forest, open mangrove forest, agricultural lands etc. Different layers of information such as, canal, forest boundary, road and rail networks have been superimposed on the classified map. The other collateral data like rainfall, temperature, composition of beach, movement of mechanized boats /trawlers are taken in GIS environment. The integration of spatial and non-spatial database in GIS environment have identified the common beach characteristics in the existing nesting beaches, which have been used as common parameters for identification of sporadic nesting sites in the coast. Oceanographic parameter such as sea depth, sea surface temperature, phytoplankton abundance and water current have also been used and developed a Habitat Suitability Model (HSM) of the Olive ridley sea turtle in the Bay of Bengal during their migration to foraging areas. This model helped in predicting the suitable foraging habitat of the Olive ridley sea turtle in the Bay of Bengal and also to identify the use of sea turtles in the proposed oil and natural gas blocks. The present study, therefore, gives insight for understanding of the distribution and movement of olive ridley in the coastal waters off Orissa coast, potential foraging ground and overlapped area for better conservation and also for rational planning of developmental activities such as the possible oil and natural gas extraction in these regions.

Habitat Quality Assessment of Australian Submarine Canyons

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Submarine canyons have been recognised as areas of significant ecological and conservation value for their enhanced primary productivity, benthic biomass and biodiversity. In Australia, 753 submarine canyons were mapped on all margins of the continent by the Marine Biodiversity Hub through the Australian Government's National Environmental Research Program. An analysis of canyon geomorphic metrics provided the basis to objectively classify these canyons across a hierarchy of physical characteristics (e.g. volume, depth range, rugosity) separately for shelf-incising and slope-confined canyons (Huang et al., 2014). Here we extend this analysis to include oceanographic variables in presenting a first pass assessment of habitat quality for all canyons on the Australian margin, with a focus on their upper reaches.

This study is based on the premise that habitat heterogeneity, productivity and disturbance are the three factors that potentially determine the quality of a canyon habitat. For each factor we derived a range of variables to inform the assessment of habitat quality (see Table). Habitat *heterogeneity* was measured using a selection of eight geomorphic metrics including canyon volume and rugosity that are considered likely to have a positive relationship with habitat heterogeneity. Canyon *productivity* was assessed from five variables including: distance to the shelf break as a proxy of nutrient inputs from land and the continental shelf; bottom current speed as an indicator of nutrient supply to benthic epifauna (derived from time-series re-analysis of the BLUElink oceanographic model and in-situ data), and; measures of the probability, frequency and intensity of upwelling (also from BLUElink data). The BLUElink variables have positive relationships with productivity whereas the relationship between distance to shelf and productivity is negative. Benthic *disturbance* was assessed from the maximum and range of bottom current speeds, and the frequency and intensity of tropical cyclones. According to these relationships, individual canyons were assigned habitat quality scores, first separately for each variable and then aggregated for the three habitat factors. The final scores were obtained by averaging the scores of the three habitat factors.

The results show that many submarine canyons on the eastern Australian margin have high habitat quality scores (see Figure). This is interpreted to be mainly due to the influence of the upwelling-favourable East Australian Current which generates high productivity throughout the year. The Albany canyons on the south-western margin also offer high habitat quality for marine species due to complex geometrical and geophysical structures. They also benefit from the upwelling-favourable Flinders Current. In contrast, canyons on the northern and western margins have lower habitat quality. Many of these canyons receive little input from land and continental shelf. In addition, the downwelling- favourable Leeuwin Current, which flows along the western margin of the continent, hampers the supply of deep water nutrients from reaching the upper reaches of canyons, particularly canyon heads that intersect the euphotic zone. Overall, these results provide a framework for targeted studies of canyons aimed at testing and verifying the habitat potential identified here and for establishing monitoring priorities for the ongoing management of canyon ecosystems.

Reference: Huang, Z., Nichol, S.L., Harris, P.T., Caley, M.J. 2014. Classification of submarine canyons of the Australian continental margin. *Marine Geology* 357, 362-383.

Heterogeneity Variable	Productivity Variable
volume	distance to shelf break
number of branches	bottom current speed
head incision	upwelling to surface water
standard deviation of water depth	upwelling to euphotic zone
mean slope	upwelling to mixed layer depth
standard deviation of slope	Disturbance Variable
	maximum bottom current speed
percentage of area with slope greater than 15	range of bottom current speed
rugosity	impact of tropical cyclones

**Predicting habitat preference for effective management of the sardine fisheries
in the Northern Zamboanga and Bohol Sea, Southern Philippines**

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Effective management of marine ecosystems is dependent on information on the spatial distribution of marine target species and the interacting environmental variables that drive these distributional patterns. Data on species-environment associations have been used to provide both temporally and spatially explicit models of habitat suitability. The significant sardine fishery in the Zamboanga Peninsula is supported by a very biologically productive monsoon-driven upwelling off the northern coast. Sardine habitat preference as modulated by the changes in environmental conditions brought about by the monsoons was implemented in a software for species habitat modelling called *MaxEnt* (Phillips et al., 2006) using satellite and model-derived parameters (chlorophyll a concentrations, sea surface temperature from MODIS; and surface currents from a hydrodynamic ocean model, HYCOM) in relation to presence locations provided by in situ catch data. Sardine adults and larvae catch locations were monitored in order to study their distribution and to develop suitable habitat maps. Habitat Suitability Indices (HSI) of locations of sardines at different life stages showed to be 30 to 60% higher during the peak of the Northeast monsoon compared to the Southwest monsoon. Catch locations with sardines identified to be at their spawning stages had an increase of 20 to 100%. HSI were significantly higher and widespread across several regions along the coasts during the Northeast Monsoon though regions where upwelling is observed had consistently high indices year-round. Records of catch data varied in volume during upwelling phenomenon. Chlorophyll a concentration is the primary contributor in the generation of indices and is therefore essential in the identification of suitable habitats of the different life stages of the sardine population based on preferred environmental conditions. Mapping suitable habitats will significantly contribute to the development of a sustainable management scheme for the sardine fisheries in different regions in the Zamboanga Peninsula and Bohol Sea, Southern Philippines.

Inner shelf sediment mobility under moderate wave climate conditions on the southeastern coast of NSW, Australia

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Sediment mobilization is increasingly being recognized as control on benthic habitats. Biodiversity and abundance of benthic species is inversely related to the mobility of the substrate. The mobility of sediments by wave action on the inner continental shelf between Black Point (Gerroa) and Beecroft peninsula (Jervis Bay) was the objective of this study, which applied wave refraction modelling and Airy wave theory to calculate Maximum Orbital Velocity (U_{max}) and Critical Bottom Velocity (U_{cr}) on an interpolated bed surface composed of 49 surficial sediments ($109\mu\text{m} < d_{50} < 1492\mu\text{m}$) collected at variable water depths (max. 29m) in 2014. The wave dominated coast of southeastern NSW is subject to a generally moderate wave climate, periodic disturbed by large coastal storm events. Under past storm conditions (1986-2011) when waves exceed 3m (mean T_{sig} 5.2-13.8s), sediment entrainment in the inner continental shelf (0-30m) occurred below 10m depth and varied according to wave characteristics (Fig.1). Average wave conditions ($130^\circ/1.6\text{m}/9.5\text{s}$) were responsible for the entrainment of the whole inner shelf apart from the deeper areas off Warrain beach. These results provide a process-based understanding of the area with applications to coastal projects and marine management.

Figure 1: Sediment texture and entrainment under average and different storm conditions in the inner shelf between Gerroa and Jervis Bay, NSW, Australia

A GIS framework for the observation and monitoring of nearshore benthic habitats, utilizing Remotely Sensed bathymetric and seafloor reflectance data

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Recent progress has been made on conducting, analyzing and finally accepting the consistent results regarding Satellite Derived Bathymetry (SDB) data compared against a fully QA'd active sensor (in this case, the Optech SHOALS 1000T bathy LIDAR system). This mutual acceptance has allowed Fugro and EOMAP to agree on a mature and responsible approach to the promotion of the technologies, their utility and their limitations, particularly in the nearshore and highly environmentally-sensitive coastal zone. Other sensory outputs at various bandwidths have also been considered for their utility in describing specific coastal phenomena, physical characteristics and discrete properties for the purpose of monitoring environmental health and detecting change or trending. These include satellite-derived seafloor reflectance data and multispectral imagery products for discrete observation and monitoring of specific marine and terrestrial macroflora. An opportunity to present and promote this data comparison within a familiar GIS environment has been made possible through collaboration with Esri. ArcGIS provides data analysts, habitat mappers and coastal scientists with a common and functional platform from which both passive and active sensor survey and imagery data can be structured, viewed and assimilated. The habitat mapping and coastal zone management fraternities thus have ample, quantified and complementary data supplied in a common framework which allows co-operative studies and analyses to be more readily conducted. This presentation highlights the utility of and comparisons between these complementary data sources and their implementation within an ArcGIS architecture.

Change Detection in underwater time laps videos from stationary observatories

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Stationary observatories are more often equipped with digital cameras taking images of defined regions of interest at predefined time intervals. The chosen time intervals are typically too large to apply video analysis as proposed by the image processing community in the context of video surveillance. Therefore, there is a need for new methods and algorithms that can deal with arbitrary low temporal resolutions in video data.

The aim of this study was to a) develop a new algorithmic approach to the challenge of (semi-) automatic annotation in image time series / video and b) test the approach on data from two stationary observatories located in different benthic ecosystems. One of them is the LoVe Observatory, located near Hovden in the Norwegian Sea about 260 meters below sea level. Each 60 minutes an image is taken. At the other observatory images were taken every 111 minutes and it is located 100 meter below sea level in the Peregrino Field in South Atlantic Ocean about 85 km off the coast of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

To achieve a) a new algorithm was designed integrating two concepts, a generalization of the SLIC superpixel algorithm (Achanta 2011) and a new cluster fusing method for cluster obtained from image data. The new algorithm can segment a visual field spatially based on the temporal dynamics in the feature space. This allows a flexible and adaptive detection even of objects (i.e. taxa) that are novel in the sense that they do not have to be learned in a previous learning process.

Our results show that the segmentation divides the image into different categories (each category marked with a different color) representing different biologically / ecologically relevant semantics. A good example is the starfish, which is represented as a red region (see Fig 1) or the moving sea cucumber represented by the blue region (see Fig 2). The figures below show the result of the algorithmic analysis as a pseudocolor map of the visual field. Such maps are computed for a temporal image sequence and summarize the changes / movements in this sequence.

We believe that our approach has the potential to be used to build an incremental visual memory of a benthic site contributing to a first descriptive ecological model of a habitat. Such a model would also integrate other sensor data such as turbidity, temperature, current etc. However, if image / video surveillance data shall be integrated in such a modelling step, annotation of the

data is required. In this context, our method can be considered as a contribution to the technological development.

Figure 1: Segmentation result of a temporal image sequence (~20h) from LoVe Observatory with two example images

Figure2: Segmentation result of a temporal image sequence (~35h) from Pemca Observatory with two example images

Visualization of the Marine Environment using Virtual Reality and Interactive Applications for Marine Planning

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This presentation addresses visualization tools available to environmental planners and managers working on ocean and coastal environments. The practice of visualization involves making and manipulating images that convey novel phenomena and ideas. First I describe visualization within the context of visual environmental communication, an emerging and rapidly evolving discipline, and then I present a typology of cartographic visualization and underwater seascape scene simulation. While some progress has been made in the area of virtual reality visualization for coastal climate change effects, very little attention has been given to visualization of the underwater marine environment, including both abiotic and biotic resources. Ways to make visualizations relevant for work with the public and policy makers is addressed including the use of an immersive virtual reality laboratory (see <http://architecture.technion.ac.il/Visualization-Lab/>) to raise awareness of marine habitats and biodiversity. These methods involve the development of virtual reality 3D imaging that links and feeds into GIS-based decision support tools. Challenges and impediments are identified for continuing technical work on integrating maps and scenes for ocean planning and management that use advanced GIS methods for decision-making and three-dimensional immersive and interactive virtual reality. The case study I will present showcases the work of the Israel Marine Plan (see <http://msp-israel.net.technion.ac.il/english/introduction/>), an on-going marine spatial planning (MSP) effort initiated in 2013, driven by the discovery of large offshore natural gas reserves. MSP efforts for this project include the development of a dedicated on-line software application (modelled after other existing technologies, e.g., SeaSketch). The tool, when linked to virtual reality techniques, promotes greater public participation, awareness, and knowledge of the marine environment.

Forests of the sea: Predictive habitat modelling to assess the abundance of canopy forming kelp forests on temperate reefs

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Large brown seaweeds (kelps) form forests in temperate and boreal marine systems that serve as foundations to the structure and dynamics of communities. Mapping the distributions of these species is important to understanding the ecology of coastal environments, predicting consequences of climate change and the potential for carbon production. We demonstrate how advancements in seafloor mapping technology, models of wave energy and modeling approaches can be used to map the distribution and relative abundance of seaweed forests of *Ecklonia radiata* and provide complete coverage over 100s of kilometers at comparable resolutions to those typically used in terrestrial studies. Using generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs), we associated observations of *E. radiata* abundance from video transects with environmental variables. These relationships were then used to predict the distribution of *E. radiata* across

our 756.1 km² study area off the coast of Victoria, Australia. A reserved dataset was used to test the accuracy of these predictions. We found that the abundance distribution of *E. radiata* is strongly associated with depth, presence of rocky reef, complexity of the reef topography, and wave exposure. In addition, the GLMM methodology allowed us to adequately account for spatial autocorrelation in our sampling methods. The predictive distribution map created from the best GLMM accurately predicted the abundance of *E. radiata* with an accuracy of 69% (Figure 1). Our results indicate that the abundance distribution of *E. radiata* is strongly associated with multiple environmental variables and these associations can be used to accurately predict its distribution across broad scales. Structure-forming macroalgae are foundational species in many coastal zones around the world but their broad scale distributions are often unknown. Using methods like those presented in this study, we can accurately map the distribution of these species, which will give insight into ecological communities, biodiversity distribution, carbon uptake, and potential sequestration.

Figure 1: Predictive distribution of *Ecklonia radiata* across the entire study site. The blue areas represent locations where *E. radiata* are predicted to be absent while the warmer colors represent areas where *E. radiata* are predicted to be present in varying abundance: red = high abundance, orange = medium abundance and yellow = low abundance. (ESRI Service Layer Credits for background imagery: Copyright ©2013 Esri, DeLorme, NAVTEQ).

Mapping the mangrove from space in the Arabian Gulf, Saudi Arabia

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Mangroves are a dominant form of vegetation along tropical coasts where its habitats plays important roles in the world coastal ecosystems. *Avicennia* plant is a mangrove species which grows naturally on the Arabian Gulf, Saudi Arabia. The *Avicennia* is spreading in scattered areas and acting important ecological roles in the preservation of coastal environment in the Gulf. However in the last decades, the urban expansions and other human activities have affected the size of the mangrove habitats along the Gulf.

The main objective of this study is to apply remote sensing and GIS technologies to map the past and present areal extent of mangroves in the Gulf, Saudi Arabia. Additional data will be acquired through a GPS survey and other ancillary data will be extracted from topographic maps. The combination of these resources would show and analyze the loss and gain of mangrove habitats in the Gulf. Results will support the decision making for conservation and improving the mangrove habitats in the Gulf.

A review of image-based land cover mapping approaches and their transferability to benthic habitat mapping

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The term 'land cover' has been defined as the observed bio-physical cover on the earth's surface. Initial earth land cover mapping efforts were based on aerial photography. However, the modern era of land cover mapping started with the launch of the first Landsat satellite in 1972. Land cover mapping can be viewed as the terrestrial counterpart to benthic habitat mapping, albeit with a significantly longer history. It might therefore be beneficial to review the common practice and past experience in land cover mapping with a view to improve mapping methodologies and workflows of benthic habitat mapping.

Significant differences with regard to remote sensing data availability, temporal and spectral resolution exist between satellite-based remote sensing data and acoustic datasets. Whilst the terrestrial land surface is almost continuously mapped and monitored through a wide array of satellite-based sensors and high-resolution imaging systems mounted on unmanned aerial vehicles, large parts of the seafloor remain unsurveyed at spatial resolutions similar to those achieved with satellite sensors. Another significant drawback is the lack of spectral resolution: With effectively only one band (backscatter) available, we lack the ability to define and exploit spectral signatures and band ratios (such as the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index in land cover mapping). However, spatial resolutions achieved with sonar systems are comparable to high and very high resolution satellite data products.

A typical land cover mapping workflow comprises several steps that are transferable to benthic habitat mapping and typically include: i) Data pre-processing, ii) Feature extraction, iii) Feature selection, iv) Classification, v) Post-classification enhancements and vi) Evaluation of classification performance. Probably due to the lack of acoustic bands, there is a tendency in benthic habitat mapping to create a host of derivatives from the primary data layers bathymetry and backscatter. Features derived from bathymetry can be grouped into slope, orientation, curvature/relative position and terrain variability. Several derivatives of backscatter have also been calculated and employed, including standard deviation, roughness, texture (e.g. grey level co-occurrence matrices), spatial auto-correlation (Moran's I), Hue-Saturation-Intensity, Q-values and features extracted from angular range analysis. Feature selection is primarily concerned with reducing the number of features to a subset that is relevant to the problem, thereby allowing the construction of simpler, more interpretable and more robust prediction models. Our review indicates that formal feature selection procedures have rarely been applied in benthic habitat mapping. Classification approaches can be grouped into supervised and unsupervised, parametric and non-parametric, hard or soft and pixel-based and object-based. In benthic habitat mapping, there appears to be a preference for supervised, non-parametric, hard, pixel-based classification approaches; however, it is not always stated why a particular classifier was selected and the choice of the classifier might be a matter of preference or availability. Post-classification enhancements aim at improving classification outputs by making use of expert knowledge and contextual information ('knowledge-based enhancements'). Despite the fact that several land cover studies indicate that post-classification processing is an important step in improving the quality of classifications, it has rarely been employed in benthic habitat mapping. The classification performance can be evaluated according to different criteria, but most frequently applied are accuracy assessments. Map accuracy is analysed to determine whether the predictive map is as close to reality as possible given the available resources. Accuracy assessments are common practice in land cover mapping and increasingly employed in benthic habitat mapping. However, widely used accuracy statistics such as the kappa coefficient have lately been criticised and alternative measures (e.g. quantity disagreement and allocation disagreement) proposed.

Underwater hyperspectral imaging for improved environmental mapping and monitoring of seabed habitats

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Underwater hyperspectral imaging (UHI) is an emerging technology with the potential to deliver benefits for a variety of benthic habitat mapping and monitoring applications. UHI is broadly similar to airborne hyperspectral imaging which is already in widespread use for terrestrial and coastal mapping. UHI utilizes object-specific optical fingerprints, reflected from objects of interest (OOI). UHI classifications of OOIs including cold-water coral reefs, sponge habitats and associated organisms have been demonstrated at several locations in the Norwegian fjords and the Barents Sea, in depths from 60 to 600 meters.

Here we present results from a recent survey for MAREANO, the Norwegian national offshore seabed mapping programme, which was conducted as part of an evaluation of UHI for MAREANO. Survey partners were Ecotone AS, Geological Survey of Norway (NGU), the Institute for Marine Research (IMR) and the Applied Underwater Robotics Laboratory at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU). We will also provide an overview of the technical details of the system and software.

Building on UHI technology originally patented at NTNU, Ecotone, formerly a university startup company, has designed and developed a UHI-system for use on ROVs. A push-broom imager scans the seafloor illuminated by dedicated external light sources. The UHI instrument comprises state of the art scientific camera technology and industry-leading imaging spectrometers to optimize signal-to-noise ratio, dynamic range and light-throughput. Using a specially developed software package, the data is corrected for internal (sensor influence) and external variables, such as the inherent optical properties of water and light source characteristics. The resulting images are geocorrected, enabling use in GIS. These images yield the reflectance spectra of the OOI, allowing for comparison across transects, regions and temporal scales. By referencing a spectral library containing optical fingerprints of a range of OOIs the UHI-system can automatically locate and identify the OOI.

Using computer algorithms specifically developed for UHI image analysis, important details invisible to the human eye can be extracted and highlighted. This software is in constant development with other OOIs in mind, ranging from the biological to the geological (sediments, minerals) and the artificial (manmade objects). Figure 1 shows an example where a very small, almost invisible squat lobster is detected by UHI, along with two larger specimens and an anemone. We will present further examples of UHI successful mapping to date and discuss avenues for research and development as well as ways in which UHI may complement more traditional survey technologies.

Figure 1: Comparison of video and UHI-images. a) Video image; b) RGB-UHI-image, and c) processed data highlighting the small squat lobster (<2cm).

Seagrass Habitat Mapping and Change Detection using high-spatial Resolution Satellite Data

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Abstract

Reported cases of seagrass loss have increased over the last 40 years, increasing the awareness of the need for assessing seagrass health. Remote sensing techniques with multispectral imagery have been used for mapping seagrass and other benthic habitats. The commercial sensor WorldView 2 offers a spatial resolution of 0.46 meters for the panchromatic band and 1.85 m for the multispectral bands. It is the first high-resolution 8-band multispectral commercial satellite that has an additional Coastal Band (**400-450nm**) that enhances mapping of the ocean floor. A WorldView 2 image from October 2014 was used in combination with field work to generate an accurate high resolution seagrass benthic map for Caja de Muertos Island Nature Reserve in Puerto Rico. This reserve encompasses the islands of Caja de Muertos and Berberia located about 7 nautical miles southeast of Ponce, Puerto Rico (Figure 1). Image preprocessing steps included: conversion of digital numbers to WorldView Radiance, land mask, mask of zones greater than 20 meters deep, dark substratum atmospheric correction and a Lyzenga (1978, 1981) water column correction to compensate for the effect of variable depth when mapping bottom features. Also, a bathymetry map was generated using a bottom albedo-independent bathymetry algorithm developed by Stumpf and Holderied in 2003. Field work was used to validate and calibrate the satellite-derived bathymetry and benthic maps. A maximum likelihood classification algorithm was used to generate the seagrass benthic habitat map. The classification scheme used describes four general attributes: sand, hard bottom, coral reef and submerge aquatic vegetation. The last one was subdivided into continuous (with different percent cover categories) and patchy seagrass zones. These new products will provide crucial information that is currently not available for the conservation and management of the Reserve. In addition, a time series of satellite imagery and historic aerial photography will provide data to assess long-term changes (1950-2014) in seagrass habitat cover within the Reserve. Preliminary results show an increase in seagrass habitat cover, contrasting with the worldwide declining trend.

Figure 1. WorldView-2 image of Caja de Muertos Island Nature Reserve used for the creation of the benthic maps.

A new Object Based Image Analysis toolbar for ArcGIS 10.x designed for combined multibeam bathymetry and backscatter interpretation.

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For many years interpretation of multibeam bathymetry data, and backscatter imagery, have been done by hand by expert interpreters. More recently computer based methods for the interpretation of multibeam bathymetry and backscatter imagery have been developed, based on individual pixels or the average of small windows of pixels to calculate a class or thematic value, which in turn might provide an interpretation. However when a human expert interprets imagery, the human eye is excellent at finding coherent and homogenous areas and edge features. It may therefore be advantageous for computer analysis to mimic human interpretation. This led to Object Based Image Analysis (OBIA) where the objects are distinct segments of the image with characteristics of spatial, statistical and temporal scales. There are two main aspects to OBIA: Segmentation and Classification. Homogeneous groups of pixels are identified and form objects or segments which can have different sizes and shapes (polygons). From the pixel value statistics, the geometry and texture of the objects, an interpreter can define statistical models to generate a defined classification. This mimics how human experts create their interpretation.

OBIA is available in various commercial software packages, but these can be expensive and/or require extensive user training. However users in the research community do require access to these cutting edge techniques, and to a software that is sufficiently generic, accessible and user friendly. Fortunately the RSGIS library of analysis and classification routines has been created (Bunting et al., 2014) to provide an open source software platform for the processing of remotely sensed and GIS datasets. It gives access to many of the techniques needed. RSGISLib consists of 16 C++ libraries and over 300 user commands. Users interact with RSGISLib either through an XML or a Python script under the Linux operating system. However, as many users use the Microsoft windows and ArcMap environment, we have converted it to a Windows based python library, and therefore making it available within ArcGIS. This will lead to a better integration of the OBIA methodology in many habitat mapping workflows.

We present a new toolbar for ArcGIS 10.x with many new tools and functions, including segmentation and classification. It has been specifically developed for the processing of seafloor acoustic data, but can also be used with other grid-based datasets. Input to the segmentation process is any multi-layered raster imagery, for example; a Landsat image, or a set of raster datasets made up from derivatives of bathymetry. The size and number of polygons in the segmentation are set by the user and are dependent on the imagery used. The polygons are defined by a region growing algorithm, thus finding areas, their edges and any lineations in the imagery. Attached to each polygon are the characteristics of the imagery such as mean and standard deviation of the pixel values, within the polygon. The segmentation of imagery into a jigsaw of polygons also has the advantage that the human interpreter does not need to spend hours digitising the boundaries.

The toolbar and RSGIS library are freeware and are available for the ArcToolbox 10.x under the Windows (v7 and v8) operating system. Meaningful classification of the polygons using their numerical characteristics is the next goal. A tool for this is also available but system specific numerical characteristics still need to be defined. Fully calibrated imagery systems will allow numerical classification to be translated into more readily understandable terms.

Peter Bunting, Daniel Clewley, Richard M. Lucas and Sam Gillingham. 2014. The Remote Sensing and GIS Software Library (RSGISLib), Computers & Geosciences. Volume 62, Pages 216-226 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2013.08.007>

Monitoring Changes of Mangrove Trees in Rabigh Lagoon Swamps Using Remote Sensing and Geographic Information System Techniques , As Modern Technologies in the Rehabilitation of Marine Environment

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Abstract

Due to changes caused by human impacts in the hydrology of Rabigh lagoon system, approximately 41.00 and 49.35% of the originally 490 hectares of mangrove forests have been destroyed between 2000 and 2012. Otherwise, during 2013-2014, it has been appeared that some healthy mangrove trees exist along the Rabigh lagoon with 30% enhancement as compared with the other seasons. The main objective of this study is to detect the changes of mangrove forests over Rabigh lagoon by using remote sensing. To fulfill this objective Landsat images acquired between 1987 and 2014 were employed. The images were calibrated, smoothly filtered, and radiometrically corrected, and then human constructions, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), mangroves distribution and changes between 1990 and 2014 were reported. The data indicate that the degradation of mangrove cover is expected since 1988 when the bay was totally enclosed by a road. The road was partly damaged in 1990, where the mangrove forests linked again with the open system of Red Sea through narrow streams. The water recharge in the swamp was still low until 2014. The total area of mangrove forests was decreased from 490.4 ha in 1990 to 286 ha in 2000 and to 248.8 ha in 2012 while in 2014 the mangroves area was increased to be 342.8 ha. Mangrove forests were degraded between 1990 and 2000 especially in the islands and the northern parts of the forests. However, the plants are being healthy in the eastern parts of the area by the 2013-2014.

Keywords: Mangrove trees, change detection, NDVI, Rabigh lagoon, Saudi Arabia

Developing Methods for Benthic Habitat Mapping of MPAs in Atlantic Canada

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The establishment of multibeam echosounders (MBES) as a mainstream tool in ocean mapping has facilitated integrative approaches towards nautical charting, benthic habitat mapping, and seafloor geotechnical surveys. The inherent bathymetric and backscatter information generated by MBES enables marine scientists to present highly accurate bathymetric data with a spatial resolution closely matching that of terrestrial mapping. A range of post-processing approaches can generate customized thematic seafloor maps to meet multiple ocean management needs, thus extracting maximum value from a single survey data set.

We present preliminary results from an ongoing study at three marine conservation sites in Atlantic Canada: 1) The Gully; 2) St Anns Bank; 3) the Laurentian Channel (Figure 1). We show using examples from these three sites how primary MBES bathymetric and backscatter data, along with a variety of supplementary data (i.e. *in situ* video and stills, benthic grab samples), can be processed using a variety of methods to generate a series of map products. Methods include conventional by-eye interpretation, along with more objective classification approaches applied to the MBES data sets adopting techniques traditionally used for classification of multi-spectral satellite data. We demonstrate how data quality can influence the choice of method for analysis of the data, and subsequently the types of maps that can be generated. Through the process of applying multiple methods to generate multiple maps for specific management needs, we demonstrate the efficient use of survey data sets to maximize the benefit for marine conservation management.

Figure 1. Study sites: the Gully MPA; Laurentian Channel Area of Interest (AOI), St Anns Bank AOI.

Integrated Digital Marine Image Analysis and Management - new solutions to handle large image collections in environmental monitoring and exploration

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The growing interest in mapping and monitoring marine environments is driven by an increasing demand for marine resources, including gas, oil and also minerals. To render a first descriptive model for an environment, different sensor technologies and platforms (such as AUV, ROV, OFOS, landers or crawlers) are used and imaging is applied more intensely due to substantial progresses in camera development. And since most industrial ventures towards harvesting marine resources do not only require an extensive mapping study in advance to any drilling and mining activity but also a monitoring procedure as well (for instance required due to administrative restrictions of the government and/or defined by the ISA), huge amounts of data are and will be collected, reaching *big data* dimensions. Thus, like in other big data scenarios the application of standard desktop software to interpret these image collections, i.e. classifying, counting and sizing objects of interest (OOI), is neither efficient (since it is too time consuming and expensive) nor effective (because of the considerable inter-/intra-observer disagreement). OOI can for instance be some biological taxa like calcareous algae (Osterloff et al. GEOHAB 2014), shrimp (Purser et al. BIOGEOSCIENCES, 2013), megafauna (Schoening et al. PLoS ONE, 2012) or it can be litter as well (Pham et al. PLoS ONE, 2014), as we and our collaborators have considered in recent studies. But in these studies, computational tools were applied to semi-automatically detect and classify OOI or just to assist the manual labelling with a collaborative web-platform like BIIGLE (see left screenshot below showing a new mobile BIIGLE version with labeled sponges). In this workshop contribution we want to demonstrate, how we move computational marine image analysis on a next level by increasing the information content by integration, standardization, collaboration and distribution on the one hand and substantially accelerating the image processing to real time speed. We will demonstrate real time image segmentation using of-the-shelf computer hardware (Intel 3rd gen Core i7-3770, 32GB RAM, Nvidia GTX 670), which allows an immediate semi-manual image interpretation during the cruise, using valuable ship time. One important feature of the segmentation is an automatic highly flexible and adaptive laser marker detection which is used to compute pixel scale information per image (see white circles in the right screenshot), which allows to extract size estimates for the OOI. Flexibility and adaptivity for the laser marker detection is achieved using a learning algorithm that is fed by a small number of example images showing hand labeled laser markers (LM). The algorithm automatically learns the number of LM, the LM's geometrical pattern (e.g. triangle) and color appearance. The accuracy of the LM detection will be demonstrated using two example image transect data sets from our collaborators. Using modern sophisticated GPU compute power and parallelization we were able to shorten the computation time for preprocessing (color normalization, illumination cone correction) from 6 sec / image to 87 milliseconds / image. Image segmentation (see right screenshot below) is accelerated to 9 milliseconds / image from originally 18.1 seconds / image. Thus an image can be processed in less than 0.1 seconds now. This new throughput rate of 10

images per second now paves the way to a higher throughput in posterior data analysis and

maybe to real time processing in smart AUVs of the future.

Mapping vulnerable deep-sea habitats threatened by fisheries in the Cantabrian Sea, Bay of Biscay

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The complex Avilés Canyon System (ACS) is located in the western area of the Cantabrian Sea (Bay of Biscay, NE Atlantic), whose study is currently being carried out by the INDEMARES (LIFE+) project. The aim of this project is to provide the necessary information to establish a network of representative Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) for the purpose of biodiversity conservation on Spanish waters. For the effective design of MPAs, one of the main objectives of this project is identifying and charting the habitats and the biological communities that inhabit them. Three major submarine canyons are present in the area: Avilés, El Corbiro and La Gaviera canyons, together with a large rocky outcrops and a marginal shelf. Its structural complexity, in combination with a high gradient of environmental variables (from 150 to 4800 m depth) and the existence of a strong hydrodynamic activity produce a high diversity of habitats and biological communities. Also, due to the high productivity of the area, there is a strong fishing pressure and nearly 400 vessels currently operating in the ACS.

Figure 1. Coral-reef suitability map in relation with **A)** Trawl fishery effort and **B)** Longline fishery effort.

Surveys conducted in the ACS revealed the presence of noteworthy vulnerable habitats and threatened biological communities on deeper grounds (700 to 1200 m depth) less accessible to fishing gears. These communities observed in the canyons was dominated by cold-water corals and deep-sea sponge aggregations. These species are considered components of vulnerable ecosystems because they are very much exposed to impacts by fisheries and other human or natural disturbances. Fine-scale maps of their habitats are necessary in order to implement conservation measures and identify conflicts of use between the anthropogenic activities and the protection of vulnerable ecosystems required by European regulations and MPA network designs. Predictive models make possible to produce continuous distribution maps from limited sample data, estimating the contribution of certain environmental variables that can influence the presence of species. To ensure the reliability of the data and its precise spatial location, benthic

vulnerable species presence records were obtained only from the ground-truthing of underwater vehicles (still images and video records). The high-resolution maps (30 m grid) of habitat suitability and the contribution of each environmental variable was obtained on ACS area based on this methodology. These maps, in combination with the spatial fisheries effort information obtained from VMS (vessel monitoring systems – satellite based tracking), are essential to establish the necessary criteria to define management rules and include these canyons into European MPAs net.

Habitat change assessment in dynamic shallow water systems – Lessons learned and way forward

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Shallow water environments are under increasing human pressure. For more than a century, beam trawling from fisheries scrape the seafloor and in some Member States marine aggregates are extracted already for more than 30 years. On a regular basis navigation channels are cleared and sediments are deposited at designated disposal sites. The number of windmill farms is increasing also, together with the necessary trenching of numerous routes for electricity cables and pipelines. Meanwhile, visions for large-scale coastal developments are expanding, ranging from harbour extensions to the creation of artificial islands for increased coastal protection, energy atolls or socket plugs at sea. All impact on sediment nature and distribution.

Clearly, there is a need to assess how all of these developments change the habitat, the more Europe calls for a Good Environmental Status of its marine waters by 2020 (MSFD, 2008/56/EC). However, assessing habitat changes in a dynamic shallow water environment is difficult. Especially, in sandbank environments, natural sediment dynamics are high and storms can have major impacts on erosion or sedimentation, dependent on local tide-topography interactions. Under storm conditions, subaqueous dunes are mostly flattened and migrate under the ruling hydrodynamics. Similar forces are exerted on the associated habitats. One can expect that the range of change will remain within the natural habitat variability, though with increasingly new human-induced stressors, new sediment and/or organic fractions are introduced into the marine environment of which the impact needs quantification.

With focus on the Belgian part of the North Sea, this presentation will provide an overview of the ways changes in habitats are studied. Generally, this will involve integrated analyses of water column and seabed changes, based on 3D current structure, turbidity, depth, and backscatter, from acoustic Doppler current profilers and multibeam technology, validated with video observations. Complementary, changes are modeled also, based on a combination of adequate input data and fine-scale modeling approaches. In the best case, seabed changes can be demonstrated evaluating post- and prior-to- activity seabed states. However, compared to natural variation changes are often statistically not significant, and overall the importance on a regional scale remains unclear.

Therefore, the presentation will highlight the need for a regional sediment assessment framework incorporating data and knowledge on natural variability of erosion/sedimentation on a multi-year basis. In addition such frameworks should provide insight into the uncertainties or error margins of the underlying data. This is important to detect true seabed changes from changes induced by using different technologies, different sets of calibration or different analyses methods.

The presentation will incorporate research results from the projects ZAGRI and MOZ4, respectively funded by private revenues from aggregate extraction, and by the Flemish Government. The regional sediment assessment framework is developed within TILES, a 4-yrs research project funded by Belgian Federal Science Policy (BELSPO), and involving teams from Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Ghent University, the Geological Survey of the Netherlands and FPS Economy, Continental Shelf Service (<http://www.odnature.be/tiles>).

Developing Methodology for Efficient Eelgrass Habitat Mapping Across Lidar Systems.

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Super Storm Sandy, the second costliest hurricane in U.S. history, made landfall on the east coast of the U.S. in October 2012. In an attempt to assess the impacts of the storm on coastal ecosystems, several U.S. mapping agencies such as the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS), and the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) commenced data collection efforts using a variety of remotely-sensed data types including aerial imagery and topobathymetric lidar. The objective of this study was to investigate the applicability of object-based image analysis techniques for benthic habitat mapping. Bathymetry and reflectance data collected by a Riegl VQ-820-G system and the AHAB Chiroptera system along with aerial imagery (Applanix DSS) were compared using an object-based image analysis (OBIA) technique to classify dense eelgrass beds, mixed sand and macroalgae, and sand habitats. In order to determine the efficacy of this method for benthic habitat classification it was also compared to a manual method of classification from aerial imagery. The resulting habitat maps were compared between systems to determine the feasibility of using one OBIA classification rule set across lidar systems and aerial imagery. Our preliminary results using the Riegl system suggest our methodology correctly classified 85% of benthic habitats. Preliminary results using the Chiroptera also suggests similar accuracy of classification. This methodology will allow streamlined creation of habitat maps for coastal managers and researchers using large sets of data collected by multiple sensors. Testing of this OBIA methodology is ongoing as new data from various sensors becomes available.

Computational analysis of spatial species distribution for integrated stationary environmental monitoring

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Fixed underwater observatories (FUO) equipped with different sensors and HD cameras allow a detailed temporal monitoring of smaller areas of interest. Changes in the environment on different temporal scales (e.g. caused by climate change, seasonal fluctuations or sudden events such as oil drilling activities) can now be monitored for selected fauna in the spatial coverage of the image. In order to develop new strategies for spatial monitoring selected key species must initially be investigated under *normal* conditions in an intact environment. Abnormal variations of the investigated natural characteristics, measured with FUOs, may be used as an indicator for changes, potentially of the whole eco-system. In this contribution we investigate the potential of using digital cameras for visual monitoring. We present a first computational approach to study the behavior of shrimp species in a coral reef under *normal* conditions, automatically and by the use of heat-map visualizations. The approach is demonstrated using image data from the long-term observatory LoVe (Lofoten - Vesterålen) between the 1st of May, 2014 and the 18th of June, 2014. The LoVe ocean observatory (<http://love.statoil.com>) is located 22 km off the Vesterålen coast in northern Norway at a depth of about 260 m. Images were recorded at a time interval of one hour, with a fixed camera orientation, imaging a selected part of a coral reef.

Figure 2: Instances of the species were automatically detected in the images recorded over time by the observatory. The frequency of the detected species at a position in the images correlates with the intensity of the red color in the heat-map. The average image is used as the background image.

We can show that instances of the shrimp species can be automatically marked in the image time series. These computationally determined shrimp locations can for instance be used to generate a heat-map overlay for the original image, indicating the occurrences of this species on different positions in the images, i.e. their hot spots over time (Fig. 1).

For algorithmic shrimp detection we employ movement, i.e. local differences to a sliding median image, and color features. These features were evaluated by a machine-learning algorithm, since the detection with standard image processing as we have proposed recently (Purser et al. *Biogeosciences*, 2014) is not applicable for

this data. The generation of a training set for learning algorithm implicates further challenges, as manual annotation is error prone. We can show how pre-segmentation with *super-pixels* can be used to overcome this obstacle. Detection sensitivity is still dependent on local image features, such as e.g. in very dark areas (holes / shadows) lesser or even no shrimp could be detected. While this still limits the significance of the results regarding a comparison of the data from different sites, i.e. from different FUO, the results can of course be used to conduct local studies i.e. compare different behavior in form of heat-maps from different time intervals and it allows therefore measuring the

change of the behavior of the shrimp species on different time scales. In the oral presentation an overview of the process for detecting the shrimp species is given. Results of the behavior analysis will be presented. Finally the integration of the species detection and the behavior analysis into a real-time environmental monitoring will be discussed.

The Canary in the Coalmine: Mapping Eelgrass as an Indicator of Marine Health

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Abstract

In the early 1980's biologists widely began recognizing that tracking the distribution and health of frogs and other amphibians was an effective way of determining the overall health of wetland environments. Declines in amphibian populations pointed to larger problems such as pollution, habitat loss and climate change. Now, in much the same way, mapping the health and distribution of eelgrass is being recognized as an important bio-health indicator in the marine environment.

Eelgrass is a submerged aquatic plant prevalent down much of the eastern seaboard of North America, it serves as a key habitat and feeding ground for many fish species, and its growth has been declining for years. The sustainability of eelgrass populations is directly related to changes in water clarity and temperature, two conditions which are often highly affected by urban activities.

This paper and presentation discusses the preliminary results of a survey project Fugro recently completed in the Canadian Maritimes for the Department of Fisheries and Oceans, with the purpose of mapping several eelgrass areas using Lidar bathymetry to evaluate the positive and negative effects of aquaculture, boat activity and dredging on eelgrass growth. This presentation will also review alternative survey methods (such as hyperspectral imagery) for mapping benthic habitats, with projections on what new high density topo-bathymetric lidar systems and satellite bathymetry may offer to coastal mapping in the future.

Integrating Object-Based Image Analysis and AUV video in supervised classifications of benthic habitats

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As human pressure on the marine environment increases around the world, there is an ever higher demand for high-resolution maps of benthic habitats with the aim to assist the development of effective management measures. Using Refuge Cove in the Wilsons Promontory National Park (Victoria, Australia) as a study site, this research presents a habitat mapping methodology integrating multibeam echo-sounder (MBES) data, video data from an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) survey and a drop-camera survey, object-based image analysis (OBIA), and both supervised and unsupervised classification algorithms.

A number of derivatives traditionally used in the habitat mapping literature were first computed from MBES bathymetry and backscatter data (primary data layers) to be used as predictive layers. A multi-resolution segmentation was performed on a subset of these layers. The mean, standard deviation and skewness of each subset layer were calculated for every image object and exported to be used as additional predictive layers (OBIA layers). An AUV video survey was run on site and the number and types of habitats present were identified from the video footage. Based on this preliminary AUV habitat classification analysis, the minimum distance between ground-truthing sites to ensure negligible spatial autocorrelation was estimated. A cluster analysis of the OBIA layers was performed to identify and group areas with similar acoustic characteristics (unsupervised classification) and a random point selection algorithm constrained by the minimum distance estimated above was used to determine the location of further ground-truthing for error assessment. A drop-camera video survey was then carried out at these locations. Five different models implementing a Quick Unbiased and Efficient Statistical Tree (QUEST) on various combinations of primary, derivative and OBIA layers were run to generate five habitat maps (supervised classification). The accuracy of each map was assessed by computing the overall accuracy and kappa measures on its associated error matrix. The statistical significance of the difference in overall accuracy and kappa coefficient between maps was assessed using McNemar's Chi-squared test. A pixel-by-pixel comparison of each pair of maps was carried out to assess the overall percentage agreement between maps.

The best overall accuracy was achieved by the model using bathymetry, bathymetry derivatives and the OBIA layers (78.34% overall accuracy), although McNemar's Chi-squared test revealed that the models' accuracy did not differ significantly. The main result of this research is that the OBIA layers contributed importantly to the performance of models. We presume this is the result of the segmentation tending to smooth out the noise inherent in the primary layers, as well as providing smooth homogenous boundaries between habitat classes. As a management side note, the mapping resulted in the seagrass *Amphibolis Antarctica* being mostly observed in the area of the study site that is used for anchoring by recreational sailors, making it susceptible to anchorage scars. We therefore provided a map of the areas where anchorage should be discouraged to prevent future impacts on this fragile and important habitat.

Development of a Predictive Model for Marine Benthic Habitats of Demersal Rockfish (*Sebastes* spp.) in the Pacific Northwest USA

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Using high-resolution multibeam echosounder (MBES) data and interpretive potential marine benthic habitat maps of the San Juan Islands Archipelago in Washington State, USA we developed a series of metrics that can be used to predict potential adult and juvenile rockfish habitats within the Pacific Northwest region. The studied rockfish, yelloweye (*Sebastes ruberrimus*), canary (*S. pinniger*), and bocaccio (*S. paucispinis*) are highly residential and seldom venture long distances from their benthic habitat, making them an excellent genus to study using geology. Comparison of the interpretive potential habitats derived using intuitive habitat mapping codes based on geology and ROV video and drop camera photos with the isri® GIS attributes such as slope, complexity (rugosity), and aspect indicates that numerical metrics representing these attributes can be used to predict potential habitat where MBES bathymetric data exist. We found that 80% of the observed studied rockfish locations were found in 20% of observed points in previously mapped geologic and bathymetric complex zones, which were identified by applying the proposed predictive metrics. Considering the short roaming capability of the studied species, their juvenile habitats, and proximity to potential foraging areas we extended and buffered the mapped habitats in the San Juan Islands region by 20 m and incorporated this buffered extent in our predictive model, thus improving the model. Such a predictive model should be beneficial to targeting important demersal fishes elsewhere providing a high confident statistical approach to characterizing fishes and other benthic organisms' potential habitats.

Using a Phase-Measuring Sidescan Sonar in Very Shallow Waters: Creating Benthic Habitat Maps in a U.S. National Park

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In response to Hurricane Sandy striking the northeast coast of the United States in October of 2012 the U.S. National Park Service (NPS) funded multi-year projects at four coastal parks to develop benthic habitat maps. These projects were designed to document current benthic habitats, and to provide a baseline data set to measure future habitat change as a result of similar storms, and/or other natural and anthropogenic impacts. The maps are to be created using a combination of vessel-based, acoustic surveys and sediment grab samples.

Cape Cod National Seashore in the state of Massachusetts is the northern most park to be mapped for the larger project. The first full field season was completed in the fall of 2014. Over 570 km of vessel-based acoustic data were collected using a Phase-Measuring Sidescan Sonar (PMSS) within two shallow embayments (~24 km²) with a mean depth of approximately 3 m. The PMSS collects dual-frequency backscatter imagery (operating frequencies 550/1600 kHz) coincidentally with swath bathymetry (op. freq. 550 kHz). This yields three distinct, yet co-located data sets. The sidescan resolution for the 550 and 1600 kHz frequencies is 0.01 m and 0.006 m respectively. The bathymetric resolution is approximately 3 cm vertically and horizontally. Benthic grab samples (n = 219) were also collected using a 'young-modified' Van Veen sampler at 73 stations (3 replicates per station).

Due to the physically driven nature of shallow water habitats, combined with the NPS's focus on physical alteration of habitats due to shoreline change and physical disturbance, biological information within a geologic framework will be used to create the final maps. This approach is also known as the "top-down" mapping approach. The top-down approach will provide the NPS with the most easily repeatable mapping procedure, as well as be extremely amenable to change-detection studies. Biophysical map units will be created as polygons across the study area and classified using Coastal and Marine Ecological Classification Standard (CMECS) terminology and structure. Samples are being summarized by species diversity and evenness metrics as well as dominant species. For each sub-area, a cluster analysis (hclust in R statistical package) will be used to define CMECS Biotic Communities.

Left: 2014 Bathymetry from PMSS overlain on to 2010 USACE topobathy lidar. Both datasets are 1 m grid. Right. Co-located bathymetry and acoustic backscatter imagery. Sand sheet in upper right of image is migrating southwest covering eelgrass beds.

Processing and mosaicking side-scan sonar images from outer shelf environments (NE Brazil)

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We investigate the outer shelf of the Northeastern Brazil, where an incised valley surrounded by a large reef field occurs. This shelf environment is 6 km wide at its narrowest, lies between 25 and 70 m, and is covered by carbonate-rich sediment. The drowned incised valley of the ancient Açu River extends from the coastline to the shelf-edge with a maximum relief of 32 m. A large reef field of approximately 300 m² was mapped using a side-scan sonar mosaicking. The data acquisition was achieved by a side-scan sonar (model 272-TD Edgetech) towed by a small boat. Raw data was submitted to a processing flow applied to attenuate the noises of frequency and geometric corrections: Slant-to-ground range corrections by the removal of water column, split in range and length; histogram enhancement, Time Variation Gain; and finally, the editions of the mosaicking image. Data processing was performed using the software SonarWiz5. As a result: (1) a mosaic of side-scan sonar images with continuous and full coverage was done; (2) homologous zones were delineated according to the backscatter patterns; (3) reef fields were mapped and four morphological patterns were identified. Three patterns occur at the eastern margins of the incised valley, and only one occurs in the western valley wall. On the eastern reef field, the first reef pattern is patchy, in water depths of approximately 35 m, with maximum height up to 5 m and a diameter of 62 m; the second reef pattern are very circular and isolated located depth 25 m, height of 3.5 m and diameter of 20 m; the third type are circular reefs and are isolated with depth of 19 m, and height of 3 m; they occur in a sharp contact with areas of strong backscatter; the fourth type is present on the western flank of the incised valley, in water depths approximately 28 m, are elongated reefs arranged in the NW-SE orientation, with height of 10 m and maximum extension of 2 km. Additionally, rocky and sediment samples and SCUBA surveys revealed a coral-rich substratum. These reef morphologies vary according shelf depths and are associated with the dynamics of physics, biology and sedimentation on outer shelf ecotone that affected the growth of the bioconstructions during the late Quaternary.

Keywords: side scan sonar, backscatter, reefs.

MARINE SPATIAL PLANNING AS A TOOL FOR FISHERIES MANAGEMENT ON THE NORTHEASTERN BRAZILIAN COAST: STATUS AND MANAGEMENT PERSPECTIVES

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Calcareous deposits and biogenic shoals characterize the East Brazil Shelf, with biogenic and arenitic reef formations occurring along lines corresponding to sea level variations. In the coast of Pernambuco and Alagoas state (8 to 10 S) the shelf is narrow and breaks abruptly at depths of 40 to 80m. The demersal fish fauna is dominated by reef-associated species that are the main targets of the artisanal fisheries. We have used a combination of underwater observations by divers and remote cameras and records of fisheries landings to determine the cross shelf spatial and temporal dynamics of fisheries in association to mapped habitat features. Juveniles of many species are found in shallow, costal habitats, such as mangroves and coastal reefs while adults are captured in deeper areas until the shelf break. Channels and hard bottom prominent formations correspond to fishing grounds for demersal line fishing. A combination of habitat degradation and exploration due to easy access has depleted resources in the shallower areas. In spite of active fisheries, deeper grounds still work as a refugia for species that have become rare elsewhere. Fishing effort is more intense in the well-known sites, as rudimentary techniques prevent easy location of new grounds and maintain site fidelity. Aggregations of several species of snappers, jacks and the black grouper were observed to occur on seasonal and inter-annual basis, linked to biological cycles and oceanographic events and specific to determined geomorphological features. The local knowledge of artisanal line fishers regarding those sites is detailed, as fishing during aggregations mean the only exceptional catches. Recent results from red listing assessments, according to IUCN red listing criteria, prompted the Ministry of Environment to declare in 2014 a few of those species as endangered, while many others were classified as near threatened. Continuity of fishery activities will now depend on implementation of management plans. On going and future studies of habitat connectivity, spawning aggregations and habitat mapping will help in the action plan for the conservation of those species, including information to be used in the optimal design of MPAs. As other activities such as shipping and oil prospection advance on this area, this information is essential to establish co-management agreements, determine fishing territories and implement measures such as seasonal closures, quotas and protection of spawning aggregations.

Application of surrogate for assessing the macrobenthos community structure on the Sergipe's Shelf, Northeastern Brazil.

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Concern for the conservation of continental shelf areas has encouraged the search for methods of rapid biodiversity mapping. The use of surrogate variables has produced important results on several ecological surveys in which the abundance of a few components of the total fauna groups can be used as substitutes for the description of the general community. This work aims to characterize the distribution of macrobenthos by using sediment properties as surrogates of biodiversity in the Sergipe Continental Shelf. A total of 16 sediment/macrofauna samples were used in this study. Textural and compositional analysis were performed in the sediments. The macrofauna present in these samples were also identified at least to the group level. Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) was applied to the sedimentary and macrofauna data. The macrofauna present on the continental shelf of Sergipe was found to directly the sedimentary characteristics. Three major habitats were identified supporting three different associations of macrobenthos. Habitat 1 - Carbonate Bioclasts - corresponds to the bioclastic sediments that predominate in the outer shelf, exhibiting the greatest abundance and diversity of organisms. In this habitat characterized by gravelly coralline algae bioclasts of the genus *Lithothamnium*, carnivores are dominant. Habitat 2 - Siliciclastic Sands – this habitat corresponds to the present day shoreface, characterized by high hydrodynamic energy levels. The association of polychaeta/amphipod is dominant and characterized by detritivorous and omnivorous habits. Habitat 3 – Terrigenous Muds – this habitat is common at the transition shoreface-inner shelf and the heads of submarine canyons and characterized by low abundance and low diversity suspensivorous communities. Our results corroborate earlier works showing that sediment grain size and hydrodynamic levels are important surrogates to describe environmental biodiversity.

Bedforms and surficial sediment characteristics of Shoalhaven estuary, NSW, Australia

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A comprehensive sampling of estuarine surficial sediments (n=123) and 45km of sidescan were collected to characterize the lithofacies of the Shoalhaven estuary, on the south coast of NSW.

Grain size analysis showed that the mean grain size ranged from -0.4ϕ to 6ϕ (Fig.1). The general pattern is characterized by a decrease in granulometry from coarse sand in the upper estuary to medium sand at both Shoalhaven and Crookhaven Heads. In the upper part of the estuary, coarse sand prevails with very coarse sand in the shallow water and finer fractions (medium to very fine sand) in the pools. The most diverse textural part of the river is located between Pig Island and the 10 km upstream of Nowra Bridge. In this part, the river bank is composed of medium sand intercalated with finer sediments down to medium silt.

Downstream from Pig Island, medium sand prevails and the texture becomes finer near both entrances, reaching coarse silt just before Shoalhaven Heads and fine sand in front of Orient Point. Towards both entrances the granulometry increases again to medium sand due to the penetration of marine sand transported by waves and wind at Shoalhaven Heads and the flood tide deposit at Crookhaven Heads. Sediments were moderately sorted in the upper estuary, mostly poorly sorted upstream of Comerong Island, and moderately sorted to moderately well sorted around both entrances. The very poorly sorted mud sediments just before Shoalhaven Heads can be explained by the low hydrodynamic conditions experienced in this area after the gradual closing of the entrance during the previous months that preceded the sampling.

Sidescan sonographs identified bedforms especially along Berry's canal, where ripples and mega ripples of up to 10m in length could be observed.

Figure 1: Modern Surficial Sediment distribution of the Shoalhaven estuary and Sonographs of Berry's canal

Environmental variables on marine fish distribution of the Potiguar basin of Rio Grande do Norte State, Brazil

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Understanding how environmental factors drive fish distribution in space is a key element for conservation planning and resource management. Such studies are relatively underdeveloped on the northeastern Brazilian continental shelf remarkably at the north of Rio Grande do Norte State, which is an area constantly threatened by the oil and salt industries and more recently the shrimp farming activity. Data were previously collected through experimental fishing with gillnets on the continental shelf (4.6-36m depth) between the municipalities of Areia Branca and Touros (4°29'19" to 5°10'41"S; 35°21'24" to 36°58'31"W) on the northern coast of Rio Grande do Norte State, northeast of Brazil. The surveys were conducted between 03/13/2013 and 06/14/2014 and consisted of 42 samples totaling 1,204 kg, 2,817 fishes of 89 species. Abundance, biomass and species richness were analyzed in order to investigate how they correlate to the variables distance from the coast, longitude, depth, water surface temperature, water transparency through linear regressions and an analysis of variance was performed to check if the parameters were significantly different between the different substrate types, mud, sand, gravel and rock. Abundance, biomass and species richness showed statically significant positive correlation with distance from the coast ($p < 0,01$), depth ($p < 0,01$) and water transparency ($p < 0,01$), which are highly correlated variables. However, only species richness was significant correlated ($p < 0,05$) to longitude increasing from west to east and no parameter presented significant correlation with water surface temperature. On the substrate, all three parameters were significantly higher for rocky bottoms, followed by gravel and sand with the smallest numbers on mud bottom ($p < 0,05$). Results corroborate related literature and the higher number of species on the eastern side of the study area might be related to a higher number of areas of gravel and rock that usually harbors larger numbers of species. Nevertheless, it is important to consider the presence of effluents arising from the petrochemical complex, which could affect the observed parameters. With this in mind, further analyzes will be conducted to generate more robust models to help comprehending the fish distributions in this area and focus on actions for conservation and management of resources.

Keywords: fish communities, substrate association, experimental fishing.

Processing and mosaicking side-scan sonar images from outer shelf environments (NE Brazil)

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We investigate the outer shelf of the Northeastern Brazil, where an incised valley surrounded by a large reef field occurs. This shelf environment is 6 km wide at its narrowest, lies between 25 and 70 m, and is covered by carbonate-rich sediment. The drowned incised valley of the ancient Açu River extends from the coastline to the shelf-edge with a maximum relief of 32 m. A large reef field of approximately 300 m² was mapped using a side-scan sonar mosaicking. The data acquisition was achieved by a side-scan sonar (model 272-TD Edgetech) towed by a small boat. Raw data was submitted to a processing flow applied to attenuate the noises of frequency and geometric corrections: Slant-to-ground range corrections by the removal of water column, split in range and length; histogram enhancement, Time Variation Gain; and finally, the editions of the mosaicking image. Data processing was performed using the software SonarWiz5. As a result: (1) a mosaic of side-scan sonar images with continuous and full coverage was done; (2) homologous zones were delineated according to the backscatter patterns; (3) reef fields were mapped and four morphological patterns were identified. Three patterns occur at the eastern margins of the incised valley, and only one occurs in the western valley wall. On the eastern reef field, the first reef pattern is patchy, in water depths of approximately 35 m, with maximum height up to 5 m and a diameter of 62 m; the second reef pattern are very circular and isolated located depth 25 m, height of 3.5 m and diameter of 20 m; the third type are circular reefs and are isolated with depth of 19 m, and height of 3 m; they occur in a sharp contact with areas of strong backscatter; the fourth type is present on the western flank of the incised valley, in water depths approximately 28 m, are elongated reefs arranged in the NW-SE orientation, with height of 10 m and maximum extension of 2 km. Additionally, rocky and sediment samples and SCUBA surveys revealed a coral-rich substratum. These reef morphologies vary according shelf depths and are associated with the dynamics of physics, biology and sedimentation on outer shelf ecotone that affected the growth of the bioconstructions during the late Quaternary.

Keywords: side scan sonar, backscatter, reefs.

Analysis of the relationship between the Açú incised-valley and adjacent reef fields in an outer shelf environment through patterns of multibeam backscatter and morphologies (NE Brazil)

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Multibeam data provide a detailed seafloor topography and mapping of the acoustic characteristics of the seabed. This study deals with the hydroacoustic mapping of the outer shelf of the Potiguar Basin, northeastern Brazil. The study area is 30 km offshore, at depths between 20m and 70m (shelf-break) and has an area of approximately 45 km². Backscattering data of a multibeam sonar system (Reson SeaBat 8124 model) was acquired, with operating frequency of 200 kHz. A processing flow was applied using the software SonarWiz 5 and Hypack 2914 and followed by interpretation and vectorization of the acoustic images. The sonographic mosaic allowed the study of the morphology and the spatial distribution of the incised valley and the newfound reefs. Sea floor sediment samples were used to correlate the different backscatter patterns. The results are a bathymetric map of different backscatter patterns and features. A 3-D model display a straight and narrow (500 m) valley in between reef fields. The sonographic data reveal five patterns of backscatter: P1, very strong backscatters characterized by reefs, P2 are very strong backscatters (very light tones), P3 are the strong backscatters (light tones), P4 are the weak backscatters (dark tones) and P5 are very weak (very dark tones). The reefs appear commonly in patchy pattern and vary as isolated, circular or connected. They also occur aligned obliquely near the Açú Incise valley. Previous data and the new morphological analysis suggest lithological control on valley incision and a depth control on the development of reef morphological patterns.

Keywords: Backscatter, reef, Incise valley, multibeam

Echo-character study of Amazonian region using Sub-Bottom data
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The terminology echo-character is the set of physical characteristics of reflected echo that is the result of interaction between the sea floor and the energy pulse from high-resolution acoustic source. The received echo type (intensity and shape) are important for the geologic characterization of subsurface, then it is necessary for substantial study of sedimentary processes in underwater areas. Therefore, identifying and mapping the substratum characteristics from acoustic signals and different reflected echo are important to understanding of depositional and erosive processes of Amazonian water bodies. Then, the research object was to identify the partners of main echo-characters in 19 seismic profiles and to understand the distribution of them into Pará River and Tocantins River mouth. The seismic data collection was done by using the acoustic profiler Sub-Bottom Profiler SB-0512 that functioned mainly between the frequencies 0.5–8.0 kHz/5, 0.5–6.0 kHz/20, 0.5–4.5 kHz/50, 0.5–6.0 kHz/9 and 0.7–12.0 kHz/20. 116 sedimentary samples also were collected to contribute to identify the bed composition. The profiles characterization and echo-character categorization followed the criteria that were defined by Souza (2006). The analyzed parameters were thickness, roughness, continuity, presence of diffraction hyperboles and subsurface reflectors and their duplicity, water depth at the investigated area, signal amplitude and wavelength of transducer emitted acoustic signal. The analyze of seismic data and collected sediment allows the selection of acoustic answers of substratum and their categorization in 4 categories of echo-character: A, B, C and D. The echo patterns were divided according to: characteristics of send signals, sediment properties, bed irregularity and presence/absence of sub-reflectors. In addition to this, identifying and mapping sonographic patterns of 15 echo-character types was possible. The types of echo less often are those with very irregular bed and small (or even no) penetration of acoustic sound. The echo types A and B were more observed in the seismic profiles than C and D in the study area. Particularly, the types C1 and D1 were found only in 2 profiles: the type C1 was characterized by presence of diffraction hyperboles and the type D1 shows acoustic answer from large sediment deposits (Table 1).

Table 1: Representation of each type of echo-character and their characteristics.

Echo-character type	Characteristics
A1	A. Little irregularities on the bed; absence of sub-superficial reflectors; average depth of 30m; sharp and well-defined visualization of bed surface; primary reflector with thickness about 2m; below the bottom, there are multiple reflections and relative penetration of acoustic signal.
B1	B. Little irregularities on the bed; presence of sub-superficial reflectors; average depth of 30m; primary reflector with thickness between 1 m and 2m; sharp and well-defined visualization with continuous bed; presence of sub-reflectors, multiple reflections and places with little penetration of acoustic signal.
C1	C. Bed very irregular; good visualization/definition; absence of sub-superficial reflectors; multiple reflections; little or no penetration of acoustic signal. The type C1 shows bed with irregular hyperboles with small dimensions.
D1	Presence of sub-superficial reflectors; irregular bed with 30 m depth; sharp visualization; primary reflector with 2m thickness; horizontal reflectors; multiple reflections and moderate penetration of acoustic signal. The type C1 shows big ripples.

Each type of echo-character is linked with a different bed surface; the latter is linked with sedimentary process. In Amazonian region (Pará River and Tocantins River), geological characteristics contribute for the observed reflective behavior.

**GEOACOUSTICS DATA ANALYSIS: A COMPARISON BETWEEN
BACKSCATTER DATA AND SIDE SCAN IMAGES FOR SEAFLOOR
CHARACTERIZATION AT BARRA DA LAGOA – MOÇAMBIQUE BEACHES,
SOUTHERN BRAZIL.**

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Abstract: This paper compares backscatter data and side scan images to characterize the seafloor substrate using data from a phase differencing bathymetric sonar. The study area is the inner shelf of Barra da Lagoa – Moçambique beaches, at the northeast of Santa Catarina Island, southern Brazil. The data was collected by an EdgeTech® 4600 interferometric sonar, 540 KHz, which outputs side scan sonar images and swath bathymetry, covering a surface of about 3 and 4 times the width of the water depth. An area of approximately 12 km² was surveyed with 100% of coverage using, as interface, Hypack®2013 and Discover® softwares. Side scan images were processed with SonarWiz5® and classified with SonarClass, being the backscatter data extracted from swath bathymetry with Hypack®. The preliminary results show an inner shelf dominated by fine sediments, but containing brighter patches of coarse grain rippled sediments. Those ripples present lengths ranging from 0.70 to 1.20 m and height from 0.3 to 0.6 m. These brighter patches, that present an intenser acoustic signature, recognized in the side scan images, supervised and unsupervised classification as well in mosaicked image originated by the backscatter data, reflects the relation between sediment size and acoustic signature. The different bottom types were validated with ground-truthing stations, with the coarsest sediments having median size of 1 mm (coarse sand) and presenting intenser acoustic signature and the finest, 0.2 mm (fine sand) with lower acoustic signature. These major features were identified as rippled scour depressions or sorted bedforms, in accordance with the literature. They are perpendicular to the shoreline and occur from centre to south of Barra da Lagoa – Moçambique system, in depths ranging from 15 to 3 m. Also, is shown how the combination of side scan and backscatter images gives valuable information about the sediment type, characterizing the seafloor.

Keywords: Seabed Sediment; Inner Shelf; Ripples Scour Depressions; Interferometric Sonar.

Assembling data on sea-bed substrates of the European Seas

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Increased human activities in marine and coastal areas have altered marine ecosystems worldwide. Effective management of the sea areas is essential to ensure sustainable use of marine resources and health of the seas. The European Union's (EU) Marine Strategy Framework Directive aspires to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) of the EU's marine waters by 2020. Nevertheless, it has been acknowledged that the poor access to data on the marine environment is a handicap to government decision-making, a barrier to scientific understanding and a break on the economy. The sustainable management of the broad marine areas requires spatial datasets covering all marine areas. Consequently the European Commission adopted the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) in 2009 to combine dispersed marine data into publicly available datasets.

The second phase of the EMODnet -Geology project commenced in 2013 and it will continue for 3 years. The partnership includes 30 countries and 36 marine organizations. The partners, mainly from the marine departments of the geological surveys of Europe (through the Association of European Geological Surveys – EuroGeoSurveys), assemble marine geological information at a scale of 1:250,000 from all European sea areas (e.g. the White Sea, Baltic Sea, Barents Sea, the Iberian Coast, and the Mediterranean Sea within EU waters). In comparison to the urEMODnet project (2009-2012) the data will be more detailed and aim to cover much larger area.

The project includes producing the first seabed substrate map for the European Seas, as well as data/map showing sedimentation rates at the seabed. The data is central not only for geologists but also for others interested in marine sediments like marine managers and habitat mappers. A 1:250,000 GIS layer on seabed substrates will be delivered in the portal, in addition to the existing 1:1 million map layer from the previous phase that will be updated with data from the new sea areas. Besides the data on sea-bed substrates, the project will produce data on gap areas where more mapping efforts should be places in future. A confidence assessment will be applied to all areas to identify the information that underpins the geological interpretations.

Further information about the EMODnet-Geology 2 project is available on the webpage: (<http://www.emodnet-geology.eu/>).

Seascape mapping using bathymetric data from onboard maps

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One of the limitations for Marine Protected Areas management is the limited knowledge about the spatial distribution of benthic habitats, whose structure varies with depth, substrate type and hydrodynamic regime. This variability affects the composition of benthic community and consequently their ecological functions and ability to produce goods and services. To safeguard the functionality of seascape is necessary to adapt management actions to their spatial characteristics. The seascape mapping in clear water is usually performed by remote sensing. In turbid waters, however, hydroacoustic sensors are required. Recently, the use of bathymetric data from multibeam echosounders have been used for spatial modeling of benthic habitats, classified according to their geomorphological characteristics. In this work we used bathymetric data available in five onboard maps (scale 1:5000), published by the Directorate of Hydrography and Navigation, subordinated to Navy of Brazil, for mapping benthic habitats on the inner shelf. The purpose was to support the definition of a Marine Protected Area created by the municipality of Ilhéus in southern Bahia, Brazil. The bathymetric data from five onboard maps were vectorized and interpolated by ordinary kriging for creation of a Digital Elevation Model (DEM). The DEM was used in preparing two spatial models: Bathymetric Position Index (BPI), further classified into five classes (depression, slope, plain, top, peak) and Roughness Index (RI), classified into two classes (smooth, rough). The intersection between those models generated the Map of Potential Benthic Habitats in macroscale with seven classes (channel, foothill, cliff, soft bottom, sandbank, plateau, crest) (Fig. 1). We identify three groups of reefs in the mapped area. The first consists of the crystalline basement outcrops that dominate the shallow waters. The second is made by two sandstone reefs to 23 and 38 m depth in the southern part of the map. We can identify three groups of reefs in the mapped area. The first consists of the crystalline basement outcrops that dominate the shallow waters. The second is made by two beachrock reefs at 21 and 27 m depth located in the southern part of the map. And the third, formed by outcrops of volcanic rock near shelf break, is close to 40 m depth. Our results demonstrated the feasibility of using onboard maps in the development of spatial models representing potential marine habitats macroscale, classified according to their geomorphological characteristics.

Fig. 1: Map of seascape at Ilhéus City (Bahia, Brazil), until forty three meters deep.

Habitat mapping with acoustic and images in marine protected areas

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The marine protected areas have a fundamental role not only in the conservation of species, but also exporting biomass, which can be used as fisheries resources. The spillover effect and recruitment of fish in the areas surrounding the exclusion of fishing on the reefs are reported in literature. Currently the managers of marine protected areas make their decisions in the context of the ecosystem principles, instead of considering sources of impact only. Thus, the mapping of habitats nearshore and insular is important for the understanding of ecosystem dynamics. The objective of this study was to develop a low-cost underwater image acquisition system using a depressor towed wing hosting a digital camera during the SSS surveys. From June to October/2014, was built and tested the prototype of towed depressor wing named "GHost" to host digital cameras GoPro®. This prototype takes a laser source of two points, with 650 nm length wave, separated by the distance of 200 mm, used to measure the structures observed in the recorded images. Six surveys were carried in Laje de Santos Marine State Park (LSMSP) located 21 NM offshore south Santos city, Brazil. The seabed imaging was performed with Starfish® towfish SSS systems, 990 kHz CHIRP, horizontal and vertical beam width 0.3° and 60°, respectively, transducer angle tilted down 30° from horizontal and Humminbird® 998c HD SI with attached transducer, imagery (455/800 kHz), dual beam (83/200 kHz) and downward-looking sonar data. The GHost was towed by small boat at a speed 2.0 knots, covering the single tracks performed with the SSS at depths ranging from 3 to 40 m and the swath width was 70 m. The SSS images and recorded videos were later displayed in a synchronized way and we could see part of the water column and seabed in dual recognition through this system. The layback adjustments were performed to project the imagery more accurately from SSS GPS receiver, thus, it was possible the mapping with descriptive details of fauna habitats and identification of some structures. The GHost was able to perform blind flights on the maximum depth of 15m and met the hydrodynamic efficiency requirements, cost-effective construction, using recycled materials, small size, ease of transport and manually operable. The camera filter for the blue color was fundamental to acquire quality video images and was directly related to the visibility of the water. The duration ranged from 5 to 10 min for each video, covering <10% of the track planned for imaging with the SSS, thus, some targets weren't viewed because the camera has a smaller swath width compared to the SSS range. The classification of sand, hardbottom habitats and school of fish based on data collected at LSMSP using the combined sidescan/towed camera system was coincident in its entirety and show great potential to mapping shallow water (Figure 1). Other important issue was due to increased noise, thermocline and lower resolution for specific targets, e.g., polyamide fishing nets without the ropes or was stretched out, covering rocky outcrops. In shallower depths the 990 kHz sidescan provided higher resolution for enhanced image definition and target detection with 70 m swath width, while the 440/880 kHz sidescan reached greater range, but with significant loss of resolution for detection of details beyond 30 m depth.

Key-words: sidescan, towed depressor wing, habitats, video, mapping, cost-effective, fauna

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Figura 1 – The school of fish in water column, detected by sonar, had the image captured by towed wing camera - GHost.

MARINE HABITAT MAPPING AS CONTRIBUTION TO NATIONAL ECOSYSTEMS MAP (1:100.0000): COLOMBIA

Santiago Millán, Carolina García-Valencia, María Alejandra Ocampo, David Morales, Liliana Barreto & Constanza Ricaute

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Aware of the need to consolidate a monitoring of ecosystems and environmental information tools, Colombia has been working on mapping ecosystems at regional scales as an important input for land planning and scientific and information support for environmental policy responsible to address more effective actions. A first version scale 1:500.000 on 2007 of National Ecosystems map, was ensue by 1:100.000 version on 2014. The last version has a marine component of national landscape, developed by the Marine and Coastal Research Institute INVEMAR. The marine research team was constituted by a multidisciplinary group which worked in generate thematic attributes from four components which corresponding the base information to analyzed to determine ecological units as marine habitats. The methodology developed was a customization of Coastal and Marine Ecological Classification Standard (CMECS v.4) from 2012 prepared by FGDC and NOAA. This standard is organized into two settings, biogeographic and aquatic, and four components, water column, geofom, substrate, and biotic. Each describes a separate aspect of the environment and biota. Settings and components are using in combination to describe map ecosystem features. The hierarchical arrangement of units of the settings and components allows us apply at regional scale and specific that best suits our interests. The biotic component is related to assemblages of benthic organisms which attributes are derived of cover bottoms information mainly but ecological studies and descriptions as well. The marine researchers team worked in adjusting ecological units to Colombian marine landscape. They assigned terms, unites, assemblies or formations defined to marine geology, substrate and biota according to Colombian marine habitats of Caribbean and Pacific oceans. Water column and substrate components were defined as attributes meanwhile geomorphology and biotic components were attributes and delimiters. For marine environment of Colombia, the analysis generated biotic and geomorphology vector layers, which were concatenated to create a new ecosystem units vector layer. The main unit of mapping analysis was habitat, defined as an ecosystem unit. We had been identified until 2014, 27 biotic classes, 25 geofoms and 117 ecosystem units related to shallows bottoms which corresponds to 19,9% of shallows sea bottoms (<30m of depth) in Colombia. The attribute table include a certainty field with a quality (low, mid or high) according to fieldwork verify and attribute updates. Some places as reef areas (coastal and oceanic archipelagos) were transforming its features and contour thanks to remote sensing techniques apply to high-resolution image satellite and recent fieldwork. More detailed and real habitat mapping was generated after updated of remote banks (Serrana, Roncador and Quitasueño) and it allow us recognize small new reef areas in the Caribbean. Presently, this habitat scale mapping represents the most updated and complete ecosystem map of marine bottoms of Colombia at 1:100.000. These marine vectors will be join together with continental vectors (terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems) to produce National Ecosystem Map 1:100.000 for Colombia.

Key words: *habitat mapping, marine ecological units, benthic biota and geomorphology.*

IDENTIFICATION OF SPATIAL MANAGEMENT UNITS FOR DEMERSAL FISHING, SOUTHEASTERN-SOUTHERN BRAZIL

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Most fisheries management systems have historically focused on individual populations within broad geographic areas. However, this process has been frequently unsuccessful, resulting in overfishing of fish stocks and ecosystem impacts caused by unintentional catches. Therefore, a new approach has arisen in the fisheries development process: ecosystem-based management. In spite of been mostly multi-species, Brazilian fisheries are managed following the logic of single-species/broad areas systems. Producing negative results both in biological and socio-economic terms, a more comprehensive approach seems to be necessary in their management. This work aims to identify possible spatial units of fisheries management, based on distribution of demersal stocks, dynamics of industrial fleets (double-rig, pair trawl, stern trawl, bottom gill nets, bottom longline and octopus pot) and characteristics of the benthic environment on the shelf and slope of the South-Southeast coast of Brazil. Potential fishing grounds with different species associations were identified by cluster analysis, using the frequency of occurrence of each species in geographical areas of 30' x 30' resolution as attribute. Bottom characteristics (*i.e.* percentage of samples of each sedimentological class) and fishing effort per fleet (*i.e.* number of trips recorded between 2010 and 2012) were mapped by using the Spatial Join tool in the ArcGIS™ software, using the same grid. The relationship among fisheries resource groups, seabed types and fleets, were analyzed by Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA). Six associations of species were found. In general, demersal fleets operated over large areas, with frequent overlapping among them, in spite of preferential grounds had been observed for several of them. The double rig trawlers and the octopus potters exhibited, respectively, the broadest and the smallest area of operation. The harder bottoms (*i.e.* reefs, calcareous algae) occurred mainly in the northern portion of the study area, and the softer ones (*i.e.* sand, mud and muddy-sand) were found mainly Southern of Rio de Janeiro. Through CCA, a high correlation was observed between the distribution of species and environmental variables, with depth (first axis) and latitude (second axis) showing the most important effects. The results of this study showed that there are marked differences between South and Southeast areas, and also among different depth strata. Based on these results, and information from the literature, it was possible to identify six fishing areas, whose characteristics seem to be sufficiently consistent to be adopted as an preliminary proposal for space management for demersal fisheries in the Southeastern and Southern of Brazil: a) coastal fishing unit: is located from depths of up to 30 meters and between 25°30'S and 23°25'S; b) south inner continental shelf unit: covers the area between 30 and 100 meters and 28°S and 34°S; c) north inner continental shelf unit: it is located up to 100 meters and between 28°S and 23°S; d) shelf break unit: 100 to 250 meters and between 23°25'S to 34°S; e) slope unit: it is located beyond the depth of 250 meters and 23°35'S and 34°S; and f) north fishing unit: covering the area between 23°35'S and 22°30'S and all the strata depth.

Macrobenthos detection using multibeam sonar for spatial marine planning around the lagoon of Venice.

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A comprehensive marine spatial planning (MSP) for the sustainable management of marine environment should start from the knowledge of the seafloor morphologies and habitats. For economically feasible monitoring in MSP, area-covering methods are needed to improve the accuracy, efficiency and overall monitoring performance. Underwater acoustic devices are widely recognized now as very effective tools to remotely map and characterize the seabed and overlying habitats. Multibeam echosounder systems (MBES), in particular, deliver high-resolution co-located bathymetry and acoustic backscatter. Bathymetric data processing is already highly standardized, but the latest generation of the MBES can give much more information about the environment than just depths, including water column data.

Processing techniques to extract all possible information from MBES full signals including the water column and the sub-surface backscatter are important for efficient and repeatable monitoring of wide areas of seabed and identification of ecologically sensitive areas potentially endangered by human.

Our study aims to find a repeatable methodology for macrobenthic communities imaging and its assessment for monitoring in a very shallow and dynamic environment using MBES data (water column and surface backscatter).

The study area is the Lagoon of Venice, Italy. This is a place of intersection of various human activities and complex pattern of shallow water landforms, habitats and communities. It is the largest lagoon in the Mediterranean with an area of 550 km² and mean depth of 1.2 m. Clam farming, ship transport and large infrastructure investments (eg. MOSE – mobile gates in the lagoon inlets to protect the historical city of Venice from floods) have a strong environmental impact and require sustainable planning and risk assessment from managing authorities. About 15% of the lagoon is occupied by tidal channels. These channels are still unexplored systems with high biodiversity and distinctive biotic communities and most of them are used for navigation. In September 2014, we carried out two MBES surveys on a natural, non-navigation channel in the central part of the lagoon, and in a busy navigation channel close to the city of Venice. Signal and image processing techniques combined with ground-truth data were used to analyze the collected MBES data. The main aim was to detect submerged vegetation including seagrasses and seaweeds, since they are very important indicators of marine environment quality. The map of spatial distribution of submerged vegetation in the explored channels as well as their height over these areas is presented here.

A preliminary recognition of the seafloor around a submarine channel: implications for the fisheries management in a Marine Protected Area, Pernambuco, NE Brazil.

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Data from single beam bathymetry and towed camera were compiled to describe the seafloor aspect along a submarine channel ('Zieta Channel') used as line-hook fishing ground in a Marine Protected Area at the Southern Pernambuco continental shelf, NE Brazil. The bathymetric surveys were conducted along profiles between 20 and 100 meters depth and around the channel. The bathymetric dataset was composed by 102.334 samples which were submitted to a natural neighbor interpolation to generate a surface. Over this surface were made 107 transversal cuts along the channel axis in order to investigate cross-axis profiles variations along the continental shelf. A towed video camera was used to generate images of certain parts of the submarine channel. The submarine channel have a remarkable erosive feature and was interpreted as a geomorphological evidence of sea level fluctuation over the Southern Pernambuco continental shelf. Its preservation is due the sediment-starved character of this shallow tropical continental shelf which is almost entirely covered by biogenic carbonate sediments. The geomorphological analyses applied to the 107 cuts along the channel axis allowed the identification of four topographically distinct segments. These differences are related in part to the erosion and deposition processes during periods when the sea level was above and below the shelf break. The evidences presented here indicate that at the outer portion of the submarine channel may be composed by consolidated substrata uncovered by sediment. It is no coincidence that the fishing grounds exploited by the small-scale commercial line-hook fisheries in the region are preferably areas of rocky seabeds with steep depth gradient. These physical features provide favorable conditions for the occurrence of more complex reef environments which justify their extensive use as a line-hook fishing grounds. This work revealed that the tridimensionality of the seafloor are not restricted to positive reliefs represented by the beachrocks and coastal reefs observed on the inner Southern Pernambuco continental shelf. The negative reliefs of 'Zieta Channel' and the other channels in the region can also provide such conditions and therefore deserve greater attention and its mapping becomes critical for an effective advance in knowledge and management of artisanal fisheries. *In situ* geological/biological ground-truthing will improve the understanding the seafloor biophysical characteristics especially related to the role of submarine channels on marine ecological processes, human use and application for management and protection.

**Foraminifera from coral-reef microhabitats of the Rio Grande do Norte
continental shelf, northeast Brazil**

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Abstract

This foraminiferal study is part of a project on the effect of oceanographic processes on the geomorphology and marine biodiversity of a segment of the northeast Brazil continental shelf. Our present data include those from hydrological, hydroacoustic, and videographic surveys, and we have collected a suite of geological and biological samples over the last 3 years. The area (off the coast of Rio Grande do Norte) extends from the inner shelf to the shelf break (depth ~70 m), including incised valleys. Within this area, nutrient-deficient environments promote the growth of hermatypic corals as well as that of multiple foraminiferal taxa with algal symbionts. Besides *Amphistegina gibbosa*, (abundant in Caribbean and tropical South Atlantic reefs), this group includes species of *Amphisorus*, *Archaias*, *Borelis*, *Heterostegina*, and *Peneroplis/Laevipeneroplis*.

The best development of symbiont-bearing foraminifera on the Rio Grande do Norte shelf is on carbonate substrates around the drowned Açu River valley (~4°50' S) and on the outer shelf (waters deeper than 25 m). Further south, the reef foraminifera are in noticeable decline. In the reefs of Maracajaú (inner shelf), the relative abundance of *Amphistegina* is >20% in scattered patches, but living specimens are rare; living individuals of *Amphisorus* have been found only in seagrass habitats. The foraminiferal community is particularly depauperate around the reefs of Pirangi (inner shelf, ~26 km south of Natal, ~77 km south of Maracajaú). Compared to other known Brazilian reefs (e.g., Abrolhos), species diversity at Pirangi is remarkably low, and *Amphistegina* is dominant only in a small sector. In the more extensive patch reef system of

Maracajaú, the foraminiferal community is apparently healthier, except where impacted by tourist activities that have physically damaged the reef substrate. Some components of the foraminiferal assemblage retrieved from seafloor sediments off the Rio Grande do Norte coast are obviously relict. In particular, brown or black specimens of *Quinqueloculina lamarckiana*, a dominant porcelaneous species (with no symbionts), are widespread in the study area. The spatial distribution of such discolored shells, putatively connected with low sea-level stands, may help reveal local sea-level shifts.

Holocene evolution of the marine benthic habitats on the northeast portion of Todos os Santos Bay, Bahia, Brasil.

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The characterization of the marine habitats in the Todos os Santos bay (BTS) (Salvador-Bahia-Brazil) is crucial for the correct management of the region's potential. Through the integration of geophysical data, subsea and satellite imagery, and results of previous investigations, this research evaluated the evolution through time of the benthic habitats found in the northeast portion of the BTS. Four habitat types presently occurs at the studied area: intertidal outcrops, reefy bottoms, bioturbated mud and a transition habitat between rocky and muddy substrates.

The evolution of these marine habitats during the last event of flooding across the bay, since the Last Glacial Maximum, was reconstructed based on the analysis of over 80 km of high resolution seismic profiles, covering an area approximately equal to 120 km². Three flood pulses could be identified in the seismic records. Inundation and erosion of the paleo-topography and its subsequent burial by fine sediments resulted in significant changes in habitats through time as illustrated in the figure below.

The results show that during flooding of the BTS, distribution of marine habitats changed dramatically affecting overall biodiversity at the study area. This information besides helping in explaining the present distribution of the habitats at the bay, also allows us to elaborate future scenarios for the evolution of these habitats as a result of human and natural impacts.

This research was conducted under the auspices of the inctAmbTropic.

DEEP CORALS PROJECT SITE CHARACTERIZATION FOR RITTENBURG BANK, COCHRANE BANK, AND A PORTION OF THE FARALLON ESCARPMENT, GULF OF THE FARALLONES NATIONAL MARINE SANCTUARY

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In 2011, scientists from the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) acquired bathymetry and acoustic-backscatter data along the upper slope of the Farallon Escarpment and Rittenburg Bank within the Gulf of the Farallones National Marine Sanctuary offshore of the San Francisco Bay area. The surveys were funded by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's (NOAA) Deep Sea Coral (DSC) Research and Technology Program to identify potential deep sea coral habitat prior to planned sampling efforts. The surveys were conducted aboard the NOAA National Marine Sanctuary Program's R/V Fulmar outfitted with a USGS 100-kHz Reson 7111 multibeam-echosounder (MBES) system. The new MBES data were used to produce a seafloor character map. Three seafloor classes are distinguished in this methodology; fine- to medium-grained soft sediment, mixed sediment and low-relief rock, and high relief rock and boulder. The two variants used in this classification are backscatter intensity and vector ruggedness. Vector ruggedness was separated into two classes and then combined in a GIS with hand-delineated areas of high backscatter intensity to produce characterization rasters. ROV transects over potential high relief and hard bottom (important components of DSC habitat) were identified. Following interpretation of the MBES data, remotely operated vehicle (ROV) transects were conducted over potential habitat areas between October 3 and 9, 2012 using the Marine Applied Research and Exploration Group ROV Beagle deployed from the R/V Fulmar. Surveys focused on Rittenburg Bank, the Farallon Escarpment, and the newly discovered Cochrane Bank located on the outer shelf above the Farallon Escarpment.

In the Rittenburg Bank area, 0.7 km² of potential high relief rock and boulder habitat and 3.4 km² of potential mixed coarse sediment and low relief rock habitat were identified by the MBES classification. A total area of 14,561 m² of sea floor was surveyed during 18 remotely operated vehicle (ROV) transects. A total of 2002 individual anthozoans, comprising at least six taxa, were enumerated from 18 quantitative, 120-meter transects. We estimated an average density of 138 anthozoans per 1000 m² of sea floor. *Metridium* spp. accounted for over 56% of the anthozoan density; 36% were sea pens. *Chromoplexaura* sp. and *Stylaster* sp. were identified based on specimen collections and expert examination of photographs. All other anthozoan identifications at Rittenburg Bank were based on expert examination of photographs and video. Sea pens occurred predominately in soft substrate, while the rest of the anthozoans occurred in hard and mixed substrates.

In the Farallon Escarpment area, the seafloor character classification identified 6.1 km² of potential high relief rock and boulder bottom and 1.0 km² of potential mixed coarse sediment and low relief rock habitat. A total area of 2,229 m² of sea floor was surveyed during 2 quantitative ROV transects. A total of 200 individual anthozoans, comprising at least seven taxa, were enumerated from two quantitative, 120-meter transects. We estimated an average density of 86 anthozoans per 1000 m² of sea floor. *Corallimorphus pilatus* accounted for 59% of the anthozoan density and 16% were *Anthomastus ritteri*. *Swiftia* sp. and *Paragorgia arborea* were identified based on specimen collections and expert examination of photographs. All other anthozoan identifications at the Farallon Escarpment were based on expert examination of photographs and video.

The Cochrane Bank area included 0.4 km² of potential high-relief rock and boulder habitat and 3.3 km² of potential mixed coarse sediment and low-relief rock habitat. A total area of 8,626 m² of sea floor was surveyed during 13 quantitative ROV transects. A total of 1,275 individual anthozoans, comprising at least five taxa, were enumerated from 13 quantitative, 120-meter transects. We estimated an average density of 147 anthozoans per 1000 m² of sea floor. *Metridium* spp. accounted for over 79% of the anthozoan density; almost 20% were sea pens. *Antipathes dendrochristos* was identified based on specimen collections and expert examination

of photographs. All other anthozoan identifications at Cochrane Bank were based on expert examination of photographs and video. Sea pens occurred predominately in mixed and soft substrate, while the rest of the anthozoans occurred in hard and mixed substrates.

Coastal Data Management for Benthic Habitat Mapping

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One of the key aspects of mapping benthic habitats, especially in coastal zones, is the gathering and management different types of data and information in a same base in order to perform multi-scale and multi-layer analysis. Since marine benthic environments don't usually have clear borders or boundaries, the segmentation and classification of habitats should be based on the complex relationship of geodata, acquired with a whole spectrum of sources, scales, semantics and resolution. The use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) could address such issue, allowing the creation of structured data models necessary to perform multi-data habitat modeling.

The "ARACA project" (Biodiversity and functioning of a subtropical coastal ecosystem: subsidies for integrated management) is a multi-disciplinary program of biodiversity assessment of a small bay in Sao Paulo coast (Brazil). The main objective of the project is to use a restricted key area to understand how a coastal region functions in systemic terms, considering physical, biological, and social processes, such as circulation, sediment transport, trophic interactions, matter and energy flows, and fisheries production and dynamics, among other subjects. Simultaneous gathering and analysis of all produced data will allow this region to be investigated from a unified viewpoint, that is, to examine issues related to the present state of the area and its ecological, social, economic, and political importance, thus permitting a dialogue between science and decision-makers. For this propose, the project was divided in 12 thematic modules considering the area as a model for the study defining parameters for habitat mapping with future applications to other regions.

The complexity of the project required a structured framework of data and information management that should be created in order to 1- develop and implement a semantic and ontology representation of the data that could allow the *convergence and interoperability* between the thematic modules of the project toward a complex habitat mapping 2- develop a data and metadata catalog infrastructure to guide the collection, storage and distribution of data within the project modules 3- Organize and establish relevant parameters to correlate and interoperable different types of data (i.e. define gaps, address sampling and acquisition of new data and information) 4- Develop a web based map server (geotlas) to distribute and visualize the geodata between the modules and 5- provide a theoretical background to develop a multi information habitat mapping model .

All information layers were organized in ESRI's Marine data Model (MDM) platform in raster, vector and non-spatial formats. In total the project have more than 240 information layers was created which could be accessed, visualized and downloaded from a GeoPortal based on Arcgis Online server. The integration of all data allow the employment of different analysis algorithms and multivariate and multicriteria approaches that could improve habitat mapping and coastal and marine landscape characterization.

The epibenthic community from habitats with different granulometry at the continental shelf of the Rio Grande do Norte state, NE Brazil

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The continental shelf at Rio Grande do Norte (RN) state, NE Brazil, comprises different sea bottom structures, such as submerged dunes, reef banks, valleys, which is inhabited by a rich community of benthic invertebrates. The present study is part of the INCT AmbTropic, and aims to evaluate the structure of epibenthic communities from three areas with distinct sedimentological characteristics off the Açu River at the Continental Shelf of RN. Sampling was carried out in May 2014 (rainy season) at three areas with different types of substrate. According to figure 1A e 1B, area 1 is located West to the Açu River Valley and shows bioclastic sands (carbonate content > 70%); area 2, on the valley, shows terrigenous (carbonate < 30%) to bioclastic (carbonates > 70%) mud; and area 3, on the East of the valley, had silici-bioclastic (30-50% carbonates) to bio-siliciclastic (50 to 70% carbonates) sands. Fifteen trawls were performed, five in each area. A bottom trawl (mesh - 3.0 cm and 2.0 cm in the collector bag) was dragged from approximately 10 to 40 minutes. All epibenthic fauna collected was fixed in 96% ethanol and identified to species level. The areas were compared in relation to abundance, Shannon diversity and Pielou evenness indexes with ANOVA 1-way and Tukey a posteriori test. The abundance data was log x+1 transformed and the Bray-Curtis similarity was calculated among samples. The structure of the data was visualized in a non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) and tested using the ANalysis of SIMilarity (ANOSIM). The SIMPER analysis showed which taxa contributed mostly to the groups' formation. A total of 674 individuals from 79 species were identified. Echinoderma was the most abundant (56%) high level taxon, followed by Mollusca (25%) and Crustacea (19,2%). The abundance of organisms did not differ significantly between areas (area 3: $110,7 \pm 23,6$ > area 1: $28,2 \pm 23,6$ > area 2: $23,6 \pm 21,1$; F [2, 10]: 4,49 p > 0,05). Besides, there was no significant difference among the areas in relation to the Shannon diversity and evenness of Pielou index (F [2, 10]: 1.56 p < 0.05 and F [2, 10]: 3.69 p > 0.05, respectively). However, the result of the ANOSIM indicated that the assemblages inhabiting the three areas do differ significantly (Figure C, $R_{Global} = 0.64$; p < 0.05). The SIMPER analysis showed that the species that contributed the most for the group formation were: the echinodermata *Leodia sexiesperforata* (64%) in siliciobioclastic sand (area 1); the snail *Strombus pugilis* (73%) in the terrigenous mud (area 2); and the clam *Pinctada imbricata* (17%) and the crab *Menippe nodifrons* (14%) in bioclastic sand (area 3). The high abundance of *L. sexiesperforata* (beach dollar, with flattened and oval format) in the silicibioclastic sediment may be related with its behavior of burying in sediments of intermediate grain size. Moreover, the occurrence of the snail *Strombus pugilis* (herbivore) in the finer sediments may be related to the occurrence of macroalgae and marine plants at this habitat type. In contrast, the bioclastics sands, with larger grain sizes comparing to the other two areas has the characteristic of a low deposition of organic matter and particulate material, favoring adhesion to the substrate of sessile and filter feeding organisms such as the *P imbricata* bivalve. Thus, the present study suggests that the granulometry plays an important role in structuring epifaunal communities in the continental shelf of the RN state.

Figura 1: A) South America with Brazil highlighted; B) Landsat 7ETM+ image of the study area with the three different sampled areas. Shelf is show in blue colors, red lines indicate depth in meters; and C) n-MDS of epifauna from three areas: 1: West of

Açu River incised valley; 2: Açu River incised valley; and 3: East of Açu River incised valley. SIMPER species contributions are shown in %.

Marine geomorphology for habitat mapping in the Colombian Caribbean Sea (1:100.000)

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The Marine and Coastal Research Institute (INVEMAR) is a member of the workgroup that is building the Ecosystems Map from Colombia, being part of the process to construct the layers for the marine and coastal zones. A first version of the national ecosystems map at scale 1:500.000 was issued in 2007; followed in 2014 by a version at scale 1:100.000. In this way, the interpretation of the geomorphology is an essential input into the classification of areas with high biodiversity and economical values for the country. To do so, it is necessary to use different digital depth, slope and hill-shade models to interpret the geoforms in the ocean. Base information of bathymetric data to obtain those models were gathered from the GIS Laboratory (LabSIS) and the Marine and Coastal Geoscience Research Program from INVEMAR. For a better classification of Colombian marine environments, the Coastal and Marine Ecological Classification Standard (FGDC, 2012) was slightly adapted including local technical terms. In addition, a geodatabase was designed using ArcGIS v.10.1 under the FGDC ESRI standard, adopted by LabSIS-INVEMAR and published on the Geonetwork. Attributes on the marine geomorphology component into vector layer include: a) Tectonic Setting, b) Physiographic Setting, c) Geoform, d) Origin, e) Cod_MEC and f) Uncertainty. Given the lack of information and the need of its update, it was necessary to create the Uncertainty field; it permits show the confidence on the interpretation of the geoforms to advanced users. The greatest advance in this topic was at reef areas, since the characterization of these places had an approach from ecological points of view since the past century, allowing the classification of units in detailed scales (1:15.000). Multibeam information made available by the National Hydrocarbon Agency (ANH) allowed the classification of geomorphology units and processes in a detailed level for the continental shelf in front of Córdoba, Bolívar, Atlántico and Magdalena departments. Until now, with the available information, it has been possible the classification of 7,28% of maritime territory of Colombia in the Caribbean Sea, with special interest on those areas with importance for marine protection and those relevant as baseline for environmental assessments through the HC exploration offshore. It is necessary a big effort to assure gathering information to detailed interpretation of marine geomorphology in the Colombian seas, through the investment on research and exploration offshore in a way that it can provide better data to the habitats mapping.

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Marine Habitat Mapping in the Abrolhos Channel – East Brazil
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The Abrolhos Shelf encompasses the most important coralline reef system in the South Atlantic. The study investigates the spatial heterogeneity in inter-reefal seabed sediment distribution and reef morphology, in order to understand how these physical characteristics influence benthic distribution. Side-scan sonar and sub-bottom profiler data were combined with surficial sediment sampling. The study area is the Abrolhos Channel, located in the central region of the Abrolhos Shelf, Bahia, Brasil. Results show four sonographic patterns that indicate two types of substrates: reef substrate (reefs banks and pinnacles) and unconsolidated mixed substrate (inter-reefal sediment). Unconsolidated substrate represented 78% of the study area, while 22% of the seafloor was represented by reef substrate. The western and central portion of the Abrolhos Channel showed unconsolidated muddy seabed, which is characterized by low intensity of the acoustic signal return. The muddy substrate area is associated with alongside reef banks with rugosities of typical convex tridimensional hard structures. The reefs are up to 250 meters wide and 6 meters high. The eastern side of the area is characterized by sandy inter-reef sediments with the widespread presence of isolated reef structures (pinnacles). At last, the northeast portion presented a high concentration of pinnacles ranging from 3 to 6 meters high in an average depth of 10 meters.

Completing the marine habitat mapping, preliminary analysis of biota was carried out showing significant differences between samples from the two potential inter-reefal habitats: muddy and sandy inter-reefal. Here, two sites are described: A, associated with a sandy substrate; and B associated with a muddy substrate. For both sites, Foraminifera was the most abundant group, contributing with 77% for sample A and 95% for sample B, among the registered specimens. The medium sandy substrate (site A) is characterized mainly by Mollusca with the presence of Gastropoda (2,6%) and Bivalvia (1,4%), followed by Holothuria (0,38%) and Bryozoa (0,19%). Nematoda and Sipuncula were described also, although the abundance was not expressive. These were not observed in sample B. The muddy substrate (site B) is characterized by a more expressive occurrence of Mollusca, when compared with the sandy substrate A (6,7% Bivalvia, 5,3% Gastropoda and 1,9% Scaphopoda, followed by Bryozoa (3,4%)). This sample was characterized also by the contribution of fragments of Polychaeta calcareous tubes and Echinoidea spines, which were absent in sample A. The sandy substrate presented the most fragile organisms as Nematoda and Sipuncula, and less abundance of the organisms than the muddy substrate, where more resistant organisms and calcareous fragments were recorded. Group abundance was higher in muddy sediments than in sandy bottoms. Next steps include the taxonomic identification of the different groups in species category. This is an on-going study that aims to contribute with a better understanding of the Abrolhos inter-reefal area, which connects two important regions on the Abrolhos Shelf, the inner and outer reef arcs.

A PROPOSAL FOR MARINE ECOTOPES CLASSIFICATION OF FLORIANÓPOLIS BAY, BRAZIL

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The marine ecotopes classification of Florianopolis Bay is a component of a Nautical Maritime Planning, which is a Coastal Management tool prepared for the municipalities placed around the bay. This classification comprises of a spatial compartmentalization that is able to assess the natural properties and its vulnerability to some nautical activities. The Florianópolis Bay is a semi closed estuarine environment configured in two main water bodies called North and South Bay. The total extension of the bay is about 420 km² and is located between the mainland and Santa Catarina Island, south of Brazil. This classification was based on bathymetry, bottom sediment texture and hydrodynamic zones and some of its derived data, being all processed in a Geographical Information System (GIS). The data used is comprised of intervals of bathymetry, median and standard deviation of 79 bottom sediments samples, a previous classification of residual hydrodynamic circulation driven by astronomical and meteorological agents given from numerical modelling. The data was standardized as spatial information and by using interpolations and a combination of variables, an ecotopes classification using ARCGIS/ARC INFO software was generated. These elements combined to generate a classification of 49 distinct ecotopes, which express a structure of bay in medium to long-term dynamics. The largest ecotopes are E41 (Sublittoral zone with clayey bottom and low hydrodynamics) and E42 (Sublittoral zone with clayey bottom and medium hydrodynamics) representing 7 % each and occupying almost half of North Bay. These are followed by the E10 (Littoral with silty bottom and low hydrodynamics) and E45 (Sublittoral with silty bottom with low hydrodynamics), showing as 5.5 % and as 4.8 %, respectively, and whose main occurrence makes up close to a third of South Bay. The spatial arrangement of the ecotopes presents four major characteristics, where the combination of the variables compartmentalize the space, keeping some coherence in the delimitation of its boundaries, showing reliability with the geological and hydrodynamics standard processes. These are: (i)The largest areas make up the middle parts of the bay, denoting more homogeneous zones; (ii)The ecotopes with the smallest areas, in general, correspond to geomorphic features and specific patches of sedimentary facies, which are placed at the zones of major channels. They contain more variability due to the interaction between the open ocean and the north and south main water bodies; (iii) The compartmentalization of the bay still expresses a gradient of hydrodynamic residual circulation at the y axis (S-N/N-S); (iv) A gradient in bathymetry is identifiable, being disposed at the x axis (littoral areas to sublittoral and deeper). The main role of this ecotopes classification is to be used as a basis for natural vulnerability and human use conflicts analysis, and as a next step towards allowing areas of nautical activities and structure as navigation routes, mooring areas, new marinas, and essential conservations habitats. This study helps to support the implementation of the Coastal Management Plan of Florianopolis municipality.

Modelling Deep-Water Coral Habitat Suitability on the Brazilian Continental Margin

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Deep-water corals inhabit different latitudes, ranging from polar to tropical regions. Several species may form large reefs that add heterogeneity to the environment and provide habitat for other organisms. Therefore, it is of central importance to know their distribution in order to manage and protect these ecosystems. During the last years, habitat suitability models have been widely used to predict cold-water coral distribution at different scales. In Brazil, despite the large extent of its continental margin the distribution and ecology of cold-water corals are currently poorly known. In addition, no habitat suitability models exist and available information from global models is based on scarce data. In this study, we develop habitat suitability models for deep-water Octocorallia and Scleractinia (Cnidaria: Anthozoa) along the Brazilian continental margin in order to identify possible hotspots of biodiversity for these groups.

Existing datasets and published records were used to extract species presence data and the environmental variables used were obtained from Davies & Guinotte (2011). Models were developed using the software Maxent (<http://www.cs.princeton.edu/~schapire/maxent>). Only one presence record for each single cell of the model (0.0083°) was used (Davies & Guinotte, 2011). Variables selection was based on the AUC value (Fielding & Bell, 1997) following the approach used by Yesson et al. (2012).

The resulting cold-water corals models showed that Southeastern Brazilian margin is the most suitable area for Scleractinian corals, whereas the Octocorallia model shows a wide distribution area, mainly along the northern Brazilian continental margin (Figure 1). Current species records support both models. These different distributions result from the different requirements between soft and stony corals and reflect the different environmental conditions found along the Brazilian continental margin. This study has deep implications for the Brazilian marine spatial economic activities planning and could be used to create Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in deeper areas along the coast.

Figure 1. Predicted habitat suitability for deep-water corals along the Brazilian continental margin. Scleractinia (A); Octocorallia (B). Guide to suitability values, from high to low: Red = 1-0.8 suitability, orange = 0.8-0.6, green = 0.6-0.4, aqua = 0.4-0.2, blue = 0.2-0.

Seabed habitat mapping of the continental slope of Uruguay (SW Atlantic Ocean) and coral mounds fishing interaction.

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We analyzed the acoustic data obtained with a multibeam echosounder during an oceanographic survey aboard the “R/V Miguel Oliver” in January-February of 2010. The aim was to map the sea floor of the continental slope of the Uruguayan Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). The acoustic data was processed with MB-System software and then incorporated into a Geographic Information System (QGIS). We obtained 3 m for 3 m grid files to describe small submarine structures (mounds and pockmarks), and also a topographic map of the entire area to describe large submarine structures (submarine canyons and landslides, Figure 1). When we analyzed the topography of the entire area we identified 4 submarine canyons and the beginning of a fifth in the south end. We also observed 63 small submarine structures in the seafloor, where 22 were mounds and 41 were pockmarks (PM). The mounds were classified according to their grouping and the presence of erosive traces (scarps), like Solitary Mound with Scarp (SMwS), Solitary Mound without Scarp (SMwoS) and Grouped Mounds (GM). High spatial correlation was observed between the wreck fish *Polyprion americanus* longline fishing activities and mounds presence. This information may be useful to define priority areas to protect by its geomorphological features, its present biota and/or ecological role enabling responsible fisheries management.

Figure 1. Topographic shaded relief map of the continental slope of Uruguay.

The study of underwater morphology of Amazonian rivers by using shallow seismic

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The utilization of geophysical methods (mainly acoustics methods in underwater area) allows the wide and continuous visualization of investigated surface. In addition to this, it is a method nondestructive, in other words, without the physical penetration necessity in investigated environment. Systematic analyze of interaction between dynamics and bed morphology by using acoustic methods like shallow seismic profiling in an integrated manner makes possible the study of features of the underwater topography with a high degree of detail. The study area is located in Southern Marajó Island, into the Pará River that belongs to the basin of the Amazon. The study was applied between the east channel of Marajó Bay and the Bocas Bay. This research used geophysical methods of shallow seismic for investigating the bed shape of underwater environments that are located in Amazonian region. The shallow seismic data were obtained by the use of acoustic profiler Sub-Bottom profiler SB – 0512 (Edgetech), model X-Star. It obtains normal digital signal and reflection in the range of frequency between 0.5 and 12 kHz. The choice of collection data considered the morphological characteristics (channel width, bathymetry and geomorphology) of Pará River and Tocantins River based on nautical charts 304, 305 and 306 (Figure 1) that are available by DHN (*Diretoria de Hidrografia e Navegação – Brazil*).

Figure 3: Study area map with obtained profiles (red lines); indication of areas in which can be found the most important morphological features (blue line) and the seismic profiles of them (L1, L2, L3 and L4).

The Bocas Bay (the upstream limit of Pará River) presented depth around 12m, mud is the mainly sediment found on the bed and little morphological events can be found as observed on profile L1 (Figure 1). At the region where the Pará River meet its affluent Canaticu River (profile L2), several islands and morphological features are observed (Figure 1). On this profile, sand is the mainly sediment found on the bed and ripples with variable dimensions can be observed in which symmetrical dunes occur with height about 4m and wavelength about 80 m in a depth of 26 m. At the region where the Pará River meet its affluent Tocantins River (profile L3), the hydrodynamic forces have significant intensities based on observed morphological patterns, ripples with height between 5 m and 10 m and wavelength between 70 m and 120 m. These ripples presents asymmetrical characteristics and are patterned by currents with variables direction (Figure 1 – profile L3). At the downstream limit of Pará River (profile L4), the bed present sand banks with length up to 180 m. This type of bed presents depth up to 50 m. This morphological pattern occurs only in front of the Canapijó channel. Before and after this channel, the bed is flat with homogeneous patterns and almost no irregularities. Then, in conclusion, the channel contribute, in significant manner, to deposition of sediment and formation of morphological features with dimensions of dozens to hundreds of meters (Figure 1 – profile 4). The analyses of geophysical data in the study area generated the knowledge of bed shapes that were not known so far on Amazonian region. Areas with different morphological characteristics, for instance, flat bed, sand bars, ripples and irregular bed, were found and mapped with accuracy by using shallow seismic.

Reef geomorphology in the central-northern Abrolhos Bank – Eastern Brazil

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Abrolhos shelf is one of the main modern examples of tropical mixed carbonate-siliciclastic depositional systems in Brazil, where the largest and the richest coral reefs of South Atlantic are located. Abrolhos reefs present high endemism levels and an unique mushroom-shaped structures named chapeirões (Leão et al., 2003). Moura et al. (2013), mapping the inner and outer shelf described the occurrence of different seabed domains, including reefs structures (banks, pinnacles, channel margins and sinkholes), rhodolith beds and unconsolidated sand/mud beds. This study presents a detailed analysis of the reef structures described by Moura et al. (2013). Side-scan sonar, sub-bottom profiler and surface sediment samples were used to describe the heterogeneity and reef geomorphic variability throughout the Abrolhos Shelf. Four different patterns of reef structures were recognized, following Moura et al. (2013): (i) pinnacles (isolated reef structures); (ii) reef banks (grouped reef structures); (iii) paleochannel margins; and (iv) sinkholes (buracas, Bastos et al., 2013). The most representative structures were the pinnacles (48,5%), followed by reef banks (47,7%) and paleo-channel margins (3,8%). Sinkholes are less representative in terms of area. A higher concentration of reef banks was observed across the north, central and southwestern portion of the shelf while the predominant structures along the east and southern portion are pinnacles. Submerged reef type distribution showed also a bathymetric zonation. In general, pinnacles are predominant in the shallowest portions of the shelf (up to 30 meters deep), with reef banks being predominant over deeper areas. Sinkholes and paleochannels are restricted to depths greater than 20 meters (at least in this investigation). In this study, 47% of the mapped submerged reefs are found in the mesophotic portion of the Abrolhos Bank. These structures seem to be undergoing erosive processes, as it was observed in the acoustic images. In areas deeper than 40m, reef banks have a lower relief when compared with shallow banks. Thus, morphologically characterizing different reef structures allows a better understanding of habitat distribution throughout the Abrolhos Bank.

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Marine habitats on the continental shelf off the Açu River Valley (NE Brazil) as indicated by Ostracoda

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Continental shelves usually show diverse sedimentary settings related to circulation, tectonics, bathymetry etc, and each of these settings may harbor unique biological assemblages. Following the GeoHab objectives, herein we aim to investigate how sedimentological characteristics influence the fauna inhabiting distinct habitats and further, if there is a geological or oceanographical surrogate, which is quicker and cheaper to measure, but strongly correlated with the biological assemblages's patterns in each of the environments. The present study investigates ostracods and foraminiferans, and is part of a larger effort, where the megafauna and the macrofauna are also investigated. Our study area is located on the continental shelf of the Rio Grande do Norte (RN) state (NE Brazil) off the Açu River estuary. Three areas are investigated: (1) area 1, located on west of the Açu River valley, is characterized by bioclastic sands (carbonate content > 70%); (2) area 2, on the Açu River valley includes terrigenous (carbonate < 30%) to bioclastic (carbonates > 70%) mud; and (3) area 3, on the east of the valley, is characterized by silici-bioclastic (30-50% carbonates) to bio-siliciclastic (50 to 70% carbonates) sands. The first sampling campaign took place in the rainy season (May 2014) and the second one, in the dry season (Dezember 2014). In each area, the sediment and the fauna were sampled in ten stations (chosen randomly) with a Van Veen grab. In all stations, 50ml of the top 0.5cm was collected with a spoon and placed in a vial with Bengal Rose stained alcohol 70%. In the laboratory, the sediment was dried overnight in a stove at 40°C; subsequently the samples was weighted in a precision scale and sieved through 3 nets: 63µm; 125 µm; and 500 µm. One hundred specimens of ostracods (125 µm) and foraminiferans (63µm+125µm) were picked and placed in micropaleontological slides. Out preliminary results show that the ostracod assemblages show far higher diversity and abundance in the area 2 (Açu River valley) than in the other two enviroments (areas 1 and 3). This difference may be related to higher organic matter input from the river.

Mapping offshore seabed sediment using Airborne LiDAR Bathymetry in Alagoas Shelf - Brazil

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Airborne LiDAR Bathymetry data have been interpreted to produce maps of seabed sediments, seabed reflectivity and the inner Continental Shelf morphology to coastal engineering, at Alagoas shelf, Northeast Brazil, as part of the Sea, Coastal and Antarctic Programme developed by Geological Survey of Brazil. The goal of this investigation was to determine regional-scale availability of marine sand and gravel as resources for future beach nourishment and the use of biogenic carbonate aggregates in industry. A range of dataset from reflectance image resulted in the seabed interpretation identifying several geological features on the seafloor at a scale of 1:250,000. Seafloor characteristics has been classified by a combination of reflectance imaging, bathymetric features, associated by acoustic imaging, sediment sampling, pictures and video records. The classes were assigned to seafloor features based on the highest quality data resolution, data availability, and knowledge of the interpreter. The following main classes were indentified: gravel, gravelly sediment, sand, beach rock and hard bottom with sediment cover. Filling the paleochannels are predominantly by clayey sand and sandy clay classes.

Politolana, a new low cost towed vehicle designed for the characterization of the deep-sea habitats and benthic communities

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The system *Politolana*, designed in the oceanographic centre of Santander, is a robust remotely operated towed vehicle (ROTV) aim to study the deep-sea floor (Fig. 1A). The vehicle operates suspended from a simple coaxial cable, available in all oceanographic vessels. For this reason it is not necessary the installation of special winches such as fiber optic cables, or deployment devices (LARS, frames, etc) being the operations easier, less risky and less expensive compare to the ROVs. The bidirectional telemetry used to control the different submerged instruments is carried out using a cable modem and through the software implemented on the surface unit of the system. This control unit saves on database all the information recorded from the different

sensors and send orders on real time to the submerged vehicle (Fig. 1B).

Figure 1. A) ROTV *Politolana* and **B)** Interface showed on the control software installed on the surface unit.

This vehicle allows us to obtain simultaneously still pictures and video, georeferenced and synchronized with environmental variables. For this purpose, it uses a video camera that records in solid-state memory and FullHD video format all the visual transect. The signal provided by the video camera is visible in real time in the surface unit (Fig. 1B), which facilitates the control of transect flight in structurally complex areas, such as cold-water coral reefs or rocky bottoms. It has also a photogrammetric system based on a Nikon D90 camera and 4 laser pointers located in zenithal position. It includes a CTD probe to characterize each image according to the oceanographic features (pressure, temperature and salinity) and a sensor of vehicle heading, pitch and roll. The location of the vehicle on the bottom is obtained through a USBL (Ultra Short Base Line) transponder. The vehicle can be operated up to a maximum of 2000 m depth and the transects were carried out at a speed of 1 knot and at an altitude between 2 and 4 m over the sea floor.

This system provides direct visual information in structurally complex deep-sea areas, which are not accessible to the classic samplers (dredges, trawls, etc). The high resolution of digital pictures allows us a better classification of the species that the video and the scaling of the image is more

accurate, allowing to estimate the abundance and the coating percentage of the different marine habitats. One of the major utilities of this vehicle is to obtain high-resolution maps which are necessary in the management plans of Marine Protected Areas. The operating costs and requirements of qualified technical team are much lower than those of the ROVs and allow us to access, in a relatively safe way, to difficult environments (rocky highs, strong currents, etc.) and dangerous (lost fishing gears, shipwreck, etc.) than the AUVs.

Application of Efficient and Portable Shallow Water Habitat Mapping System, Combined High-Resolution Swath Bathymetry and Side Scan Acoustic Imagery to Detect and Classify Structures, Repeatedly

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Combined high-resolution bathymetric and side scan sonar technology hosted by manned and unmanned vessels demonstrates efficiency, portability, and repeatability for surveying shallow water habitat. In shallow waters (from 1 to 50-meter depth below the vessel), a corridor from 10 to 500-meter total swath is mapped with side scan acoustic imagery and bathymetry using the Klein 3500 sonar system. The wide swath side scan acoustic imagery shows finer than 2-centimeter resolution with more than 16-bit color. Simultaneously, terrain bathymetry is mapped with 10 to 50-centimeter total vertical and horizontal uncertainty, supporting predictive repeatability. The system provides fine-scale inspection capability while supporting rapid response in producing accurate reference charts and maps. A digital terrain model (DTM) is generated in real-time, exposing prominent habitat features and other objects of interest for detailed inspection and classification using the coincident acoustic imagery. Identified features are mapped and classified in geographic space using integrated navigation data from combined satellite and inertial solutions. The DTM provides robust information for resolving features of interest. Using the co-sampled side scan imagery, the features can be inspected, classified, and mapped.

To demonstrate capability of this system, a submerged river near Houston, TX, USA was mapped using both manned and unmanned vessels hosting the Klein 3500 survey system. Multiple man-made habitat features were detected, inspected, classified and mapped. The initial bathymetric DTM revealed a submerged dam, a bridge structure, region of settlement, a small boat and shipwreck, among other habitat related features of interest. Further inspection of the bathymetry around the remaining dam structure exposed the former inlet channel and downstream scour region. The intake grating for the dam, scattered logs and other debris, as well as patterns of variation in substrate and schools of fish were apparent in the related acoustic backscatter imagery. Around the structure of the submerged bridge, remaining debris and trestle construction, trees, and distinct differences in backscatter between the relic river bank and channel substrate are readily identified. A prominent bathymetric feature along the length of the bridge was recognized as a sunken paddleboat shipwreck and near the channel, a small sunken boat was also discovered. An area with straight linear and right angular features near a relic river bank revealed a foundation from a submerged settlement. On closer inspection, a circular trail with a branch leading to a stockyard area is also apparent. These distinct features were then classified and geographically mapped with their high resolution imagery for habitat reference. The methodology applied in this effort demonstrates workflow efficiency and details the capability to map hydrography and features of interest using a portable system on manned and unmanned vessels for use in low altitude, or shallow waters, with repeatability.

Above image shows submerged retention dam structure inspected using side scan acoustic image with reference to the associated bathymetric digital elevation model. Both datasets collected simultaneously with Klein 3500 survey system.

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